

SURVEYING PRINCIPALS AND TEACHERS: METHODOLOGICAL INSIGHTS INTO THE DESIGN OF THE REFORMED QUESTIONNAIRES

REFORMED Methodological Notes No. 2

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This note describes the methodology behind the design of the REFORMED Survey questionnaires. The Survey constitutes one of the main pillars of REFORMED RS2 which is aimed at exploring the intricate relationship between SAWA policies, contextual contingencies and policy enactment dynamics. The aim of this note is essentially twofold. On the one hand, it provides detailed information on the key concepts used in RS2 as well as the theoretical underpinnings and content of the questionnaires. On the other hand, it presents a detailed overview of the methodological steps followed to conceive and develop them. The information contained in this note is relevant for those researchers who want to use the data collected through the REFORMED Survey. It also provides useful methodological insights that can be valuable for those who want to undertake similar research endeavours.

Recommended citation

Levatino, A. (2021). *Surveying Principals and Teachers: Methodological Insights into the Design of the REFORMED Questionnaires*. REFORMED Methodological Papers No. 2. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4450774

Table of contents

Acknowledgements.....	3
1. Introduction.....	4
2. Theoretical and analytical framework.....	5
2.1 Key concepts of REFORMED RS2.....	5
2.2 Main topics of the REFORMED Survey.....	6
3. Phases of the Questionnaires’ design and methodological insights.....	8
3.1 Designing the questions.....	8
3.2 Experts’ quality checks and development of Source Questionnaires.....	10
3.3 Adaptation, translation and national pre-testing.....	11
4. Questionnaires’ content.....	12
4.1 SAWA enactment.....	12
4.1.1 SAWA policies’ interpretation / Opinion and attitudes towards PBA and autonomy	13
4.1.2 SAWA policies’ translation / Use of national standardised tests.....	19
4.1.3 Undesired effects of PBA: an experimental approach.....	24
4.2 LEM and school context.....	28
4.2.1 LEM.....	28
4.2.2 School context.....	31
4.3 Commercial Education Improvement Services (CEIS).....	37
4.4 Respondents’ personal and professional information.....	38
4.5 Investigating teachers’ motivation: a survey experiment.....	44
5. Conclusion and remaining challenges.....	46
6. List of References.....	47
Appendix: REFORMED Source questionnaires.....	54
Principal questionnaire.....	54
Teacher questionnaire.....	78

Acknowledgements

The REFORMED Survey questionnaires have been the result of a collective effort that involved a number of people. Thanks are due to all of them.

The design of the questionnaires has been coordinated by Antonina Levatino, under the direction of Antoni Verger, PI of the REFORMED Project. Natalie Browes, Marjolein Camphuijsen, Gerard Ferrer-Esteban, Clara Fontdevila, Laura Mentini, Giulia Montefiore, Mauro Moschetti, Marcel Pagès, Lluís Parcerisa and Andreu Termes have been intensively involved in the theoretical reflections, concepts' definition, modules' and items' development. This note mostly originates from this intense collective work.

At the beginning of the process, several researchers have contributed to the theoretical reflections on various specific topics developed in the Survey (in alphabetical order): Xavier Ballart (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona), Digna Couso (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona), Isabel Flores (Instituto Para as Políticas Públicas e Sociais), Priya Goel La Londe (University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign), Guillem Ripoll Pascual (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona), Aina Tarabini (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona), Greg Thompson (Queensland University of Technology) and Agnès Van Zanten (Sciences Po).

A special thanks need to be addressed to all those researchers that have contributed with their expertise to the thorough review of the questionnaires' modules (in alphabetical order): Stephen Ball (University College of London), Patricia Burch (USC Rossier School of Education), Cynthia Coburn (Northwestern's School of Education and Social Policy), Digna Couso (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona), Begonya Folch (Fundació Jaume Bofill), Wiljain Hendriks (Tilburg University), Jessica Holloway (Deakin University), Aina Gallego (IBEI - Institut de Barcelona d'Estudis Internacionals), Jorunn Moller (University of Oslo), Christian Maroy (University of Montreal), Alison Milner (The University of Nottingham), Thomas Schillemans (University of Utrecht), Sam Sellar (Manchester Metropolitan University), Guri Skedsmo (University of Oslo-University of Teacher Education Zug), James Spillane (Northwestern's School of Education and Social Policy), Howard Stevenson (The University of Nottingham), Aina Tarabini (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona), Agnès Van Zanten (Sciences Po), Annelise Voisin (University of Chile), Wiebke Weber (RECSM – Research and Expertise Research Centre for Survey Methodology) and Adrián Zancajo (University of Glasgow).

Other researchers based in different countries have assisted the REFORMED Project team with the translation and adaptation of the questionnaires to the specific country cases: Alejandra Farabella (Universidad de Chile) for Chile; Miriam Prieto (Universidad Autónoma de Madrid) for Madrid; Judith Conjn (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam), Melanie Ehren (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam), and Hülya Kosar-Altinyelken (University of Amsterdam) for the Dutch case; Guri Skedsmo (University of Oslo; University of Teacher Education Zug), Jorunn Moller (University of Oslo) and Ann Elisabeth Gunnulfsen (University of Oslo) for Norway; and Paolo Landri (CNR- IRPPS) and Emiliano Grimaldi (Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II) for Italy.

We are also particularly thankful to all the members of the GEPS research group for their valuable support and comments on various phases of the questionnaires' development. Finally, special thanks are due to all the teachers, principals and other members of the leadership team who got involved in the testing and piloting phases of the questionnaires.

SURVEYING PRINCIPALS AND TEACHERS: METHODOLOGICAL INSIGHTS INTO THE DESIGN OF THE REFORMED QUESTIONNAIRES

1. Introduction

The REFORMED Project analyses how and why school autonomy with accountability (hereafter SAWA) policies are being adopted and enacted by actors operating at different scales. The project is structured into two interconnected research strands: Research Strand 1 (RS1) focuses on the global dissemination and adoption of SAWA policies at the regulatory level, whereas Research Strand 2 (RS2) explores the enactment of SAWA policies at the school level. RS2 follows a mixed method approach which consists of the triangulation of original quantitative data collected by means of a Survey applied to principals, relevant members of the leadership team and teachers, and of qualitative information coming from in-depth interviews with selected school actors in different school contexts (e.g. vice-principal, pedagogical coordinator, etc.).¹

The REFORMED Project starts from the awareness that SAWA policies have already been investigated by scholars of different disciplines, and that different methodological approaches have been used to analyse them from different angles and with different goals. Nonetheless, it recognises the need of a new approach aiming at opening up the ‘black box’ of SAWA policies enactment within schools. On the one hand, existing quantitative studies, mainly conducted by economists, have tried to explore the impact of these policies on different outcomes, for instance students’ results and educational equity (e.g. Chiang, 2009; Pandey et al., 2010). These studies, however, lack of a more in-depth analysis of the modalities through which SAWA policies ‘land’ in the schools, i.e. of the ways principals, teachers and other relevant stakeholders make sense of these policies and translate them into every-day practices. On the other hand, studies using a qualitative methodology have specifically focused on SAWA policies implementation (e.g. Hemmer et al., 2012). Nevertheless, the results of these studies, often relying on small samples obtained with non-probabilistic sampling strategies, generally hardly transcend the idiosyncrasy of the cases under analysis.

The theoretical starting point of REFORMED RS2 is that individual actors mediate policies by giving meaning, interpreting and translating them into practices in various ways, as theorised by Ball et al. (2012). Another important cornerstone of our research is the centrality given to the characteristics of the local contexts where schools operate. We are indeed seduced by the idea that “local education markets” operate as autonomous regulatory forces and that, accordingly, the position occupied by the schools within these markets play a significant role in influencing actors’ perceptions, interpretations and actions (Maroy and Van Zanten, 2009).

Having this in mind, the ambition of the REFORMED Survey is twofold. On the one hand, the Survey provides quantitative large-scale datasets including relevant contextual and subjective variables. The attempt is to “unpack”, in a quantitative way, the enactment (Ball et al., 2012) of SAWA policies in different school contexts. On the other hand, the Survey delivers relevant information to typify and select school principals and teachers for the qualitative scrutiny.

The REFORMED Survey has been conducted in several countries. The initial REFORMED cases included Chile, Spain, the Netherlands² and Norway. More recently, Italy has been added to the country sample³. Adapted versions

¹ See <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/680172/reporting>

² In case of the Netherlands, data have been collected in two rounds. In the second round, we introduced improvements and small changes to the questionnaires. The information presented in this methodological note refers to the Dutch questionnaires as they were in the first round of data collection.

³ The questionnaires for the Italian cases have been improved and modified accordingly to our experiences and lessons learned from the other cases. The specificities of the Italian questionnaires are not the object of the present methodological note.

of the Survey will be also applied by project associate partners in Australia, Brazil, Shanghai, Hong Kong and Mexico. The REFORMED Survey is made up of two questionnaires: a principal questionnaire (hereafter PQ), applied to principals and other relevant members of the school leadership team of schools, and a teacher questionnaire (hereafter TQ). The questionnaires have been designed to be completed online by means of a computer, tablet or smartphone through the Qualtrics platform. Nevertheless, in almost every country, a team of surveyors personally visited the schools to incentivize the participation and prevent drop outs, as well as to solve technical problems and clarify potential doubts. More information on the Survey data collection and the fieldwork in each case study can be found in forthcoming REFORMED methodological notes.

This methodological note focuses on the conception and development of the REFORMED Survey questionnaires. After specifying the key concepts and main topics of REFORMED RS2, it presents the methodological steps followed to develop these instruments. Next, it provides an overview of the content of the two questionnaires. The goals are to offer in-depth information on the theoretical motivations that drove the questionnaires' design, to present the survey's themes and to give methodological insights that may be useful for future researchers willing to design similar kinds of instruments.

2. Theoretical and analytical framework

2.1 Key concepts of REFORMED RS2

SAWA: The acronym SAWA refers to “School Autonomy with Accountability policies“. These are two sets of educational policies that have increasingly acquired centrality and recognition in education systems worldwide (Verger and Parcerisa, 2017b). Accountability refers to the implementation of mechanisms aimed at supervising people's labour through the evaluation of its outcomes, normally students' results in the educational sector. Autonomy concerns the devolution of responsibilities to schools in terms of organisational, budgetary and/or pedagogical decision-making. These two sets of policies are strictly interrelated and, in many cases, they can be considered as two faces of the same coin: schools gain independence but, at the same time, they become accountable (Verger and Parcerisa, 2017a). According to influential international organizations, the combination of accountability with autonomy policies is particularly beneficial (OECD, 2011; World Bank, 2015).

School Accountability: Accountability is defined as “a relationship between an actor and a forum, in which the actor has an obligation to explain and to justify his or her conduct, the forum can pose questions and pass judgement, and the actor may face consequences” (Bovens, 2007: 450). Accountability policies can vary according to “What level of accountability is to be provided? Who is expected to provide the account? To who is the account owed? What is to be accounted for? What are the consequences of providing an account?” (Leithwood and Earl, 2000: 2). In our project, we focus on “performance-based accountability” (hereafter PBA), i.e. accountability policies that are attached to students' performance, commonly evaluated through national large-scale standardised tests (Verger and Parcerisa, 2017). In the last decades, this form of accountability has become increasingly central and widespread at the global level (Lingard et al., 2016).

School Autonomy: School autonomy is defined as the “increase of the self-governance capacities of individual schools” (Christ and Dobbins, 2016: 3). Autonomy can have different features, giving rise to different models of school autonomy (Arcia et al. 2010). According to the OECD Education at a Glance report (OECD, 2012), school autonomy policies could be identified according to three main characteristics: 1) domain of decision-making; 2) deciding actors; and 3) mode of decision-making. The first aspect concerns the domains of decision-making, more specifically: (a) resource management; (b) planning and structure; (c) personnel management; and (d) organization of instruction. The second important feature concerns the actor/s to which the decision-making is granted (e.g. state, region, local authority, school governing board, principal, and teachers). Finally, as suggested by the OECD (2012) and Eurydice (2007; 2012), the mode of decision-making also plays a role. It is possible to distinguish between full

and limited autonomy. The former implies that the decision-maker is exclusively constrained by the general legislation, i.e. not specific to the educational sector. In the latter, the decision-maker has to consult educational bodies located at higher level within the education system.

Policy Enactment: The concept of “policy enactment” is due to Ball, according to whom “policies do not normally tell you what to do” (1994: 19), so they cannot be considered as texts that are easily implemented in a linear manner. In the enactment framework, putting policies into practice is understood as a negotiated, creative, complex and, sometimes constrained, process (Ball, 1994). One can distinguish two different moments within this complex process of “decoding” and “recoding” policy messages and texts (Ball et al., 2012), namely: the interpretation and translation moments. A range of different policy ‘enactors’ is involved in these processes of interpreting and translating policy reforms into practices and all this inevitably shapes policy outcomes (Ball et al., 2012). Policy enactment is mediated by institutional and contextual factors (Braun et al., 2011).

Local Education Market (hereafter LEM): Local education markets (also known as local education spaces, in scarcely marketized educational environments) are social and geographical spaces of interaction between educational providers (schools, principals) and consumers (families, students). LEM are formally and informally regulated and are constituted by structural properties and actors’ agency. ‘Structures’ essentially include administrative and geographical boundaries, formal regulations and policies, and schools’ characteristics. ‘Agency’ implies the interpretation and translation of these ‘structures’ by actors both on the supply and the demand sides. As LEMs operate as ‘fields’, within them all actors own different and unequal capitals. These differences in capitals result in an informal hierarchy, particularly on the supply side. The predominant form of relation in the supply side is competition, especially in marketized environment where free school choice is in place. Cooperation dynamics are however also possible. The importance of local markets in education has been highlighted in the literature (e.g. Waslander et al., 2010; Woods, 2000).

2.2 Main topics of the REFORMED Survey

Figure 1 represents the main topics of our research and how they are related. The red filled line box represents information collected through the Survey. The other two boxes indicate information coming from secondary data. Indeed, for the analyses, the information collected through the Survey is meant to be complemented by and triangulated with secondary data to grasp relevant contextual factors, such as the SAWA policy regime at stake in the particular case, and the characteristics of the LEM where the schools are inserted.

SAWA regime is the policy framework of a given country concerning school accountability and autonomy, having different characteristics in the country cases analysed. Information on the SAWA policies legal framework is fundamental to understand the ways school actors enact them. Three orders of information coming from secondary data are of particular relevance here: 1) Identification of who is in charge of the monitoring of the test’s implementation and results; 2) Ascertainment of the consequences of test scores, i.e. what consequences are at stake and for whom; 3) Checking whether and how test scores are made public as well as whether they are used to classify, categorise or rank schools, teachers, and/or pupils. Triangulated with the data coming from the Survey, information of each individual case’s SAWA regime also allows evaluating the extent to which principals and teachers actually know this legal framework. As displayed in Figure 1, SAWA policies may have a direct influence on school practices and policy enactment. This effect may also operate indirectly to the extent they may alter, often by injecting elements of competition, the configuration of the LEM where schools are located.

Figure 1: REFORMED Surveys Analytical Framework

Source: the author (REFORMED team)

The characteristics of the **LEM**, and the position of the school within its internal hierarchy, can have a significant impact on actors' experiences, perceptions, and strategies. Hence, from the analytical point of view, LEM can be considered a meso-factor between macro (e.g., educational policies, such as SAWA) and micro levels (e.g., in-school and classroom processes). From a methodological point of view, particularly when quantitative comparative approaches have to be applied, the analysis of LEM is challenging. In the REFORMED Project, we recognise that the analysis of LEM should be undertaken from two different, complementary, angles that allow to measure LEM objective characteristics as well as key actors' subjective perceptions of it. This is why, on the one hand, in the REFORMED Project, data on some crucial LEM characteristics are taken from secondary administrative sources with the aim of characterising some aspects. These essentially concern: a) objective competition, which has been typically operationalized through the Herfindahl index (MECD, 2014; Musset, 2012); b) market (in)stability, essentially quantified through the analysis of the variation in schools' enrolment numbers; and c) mobility patterns. On the other hand, information on how school's actors, essentially principals, subjectively perceive market competition and the potential associated pressure/s is gathered through the questionnaires.

This subjective perception of LEM is likely to be influenced by the **school context and characteristics**. This is why, in Figure 1, perception of LEM is situated at the intersection between the two boxes of LEM and school. Teachers and principals are acting within schools. It is thus fundamental not to neglect school characteristics. In the Survey, we ask for different types of information related to different relevant aspects, as for example, trust dynamics, collegial relationships, etc. which will be detailed below.

School context and the subjective perception of competitive pressure can influence the **enactment of SAWA policies** (purple box in figure 1), which constitutes the core of the Survey. Following the suggestion by Ball et al. (2012), enactment can be theorised as a two-phase process: 1) the phase of "interpretation", which consists of the "decoding" of policies, i.e. their reception, making of sense and evaluation; and 2) the phase of "translation", which can be considered as the process of "recoding" of policies that crystallizes in concrete practices. The aggregation of

such practices constitutes the school responses to SAWA policies. Through survey experiments, our Survey also looks at the potential of PBA to generate collateral effects and undesired responses at the classroom and at the school levels.

Accountability systems put pressure on schools to improve their results in the short/middle term, and have contributed to the proliferation of a broad range of school improvement services, lesson plans and other educational materials usually provided by the private sector – this is what we call **commercial education improvement services**, or **CEIS**.

Obviously, **individual respondent’s characteristics and their role within the school** may influence all the process, from the perceptions of the LEM to the processes of interpretation and translation, as well as their practices. This is why the Survey contains questions aiming at collecting personal information and individual characteristics of respondents that may influence their attitudes, perceptions and behaviours.

3. Phases of the Questionnaires’ design and methodological insights

The REFORMED Survey aims to achieve high methodological standards, striving to attain a good level of data comparability in the different country cases where it is applied. This is the reason why the design of the REFORMED Survey Questionnaires involved a number of steps aimed at improving their quality. Table 1 provides an overview of the questionnaires’ development process.

Table 1: Milestones of the Questionnaires’ design

	Activity
February - June 2017	Development of the conceptual and analytical framework
June - October 2017	First draft of questions’ and items’ design
October 2017 - January 2018	Academic experts’ review round of thematic units/modules
February 2018	Draft of Source Questionnaires
March - April 2018	RECSM review round of the drafts of the Source Questionnaires and elaboration of the final versions in British English
May - July 2018	Adaptation to country cases and translation
August - November 2018	Survey pre-tests and finalisation of survey instruments’ design

As shown in Table 1, from February to June 2017 the REFORMED team developed the conceptual and analytical framework of RS2 that is at the basis of the Survey. Teamwork was organised in form of weekly seminars and reading groups’ meetings around key topics. Often, internationally recognised scholars with an expertise in the studied topics actively participated in these meetings that had as a primary goal to identify relevant working hypotheses as well as key variables to be measured in the Survey.

3.1 Designing the questions

In June 2017, we split the analytical framework into thematic units/modules and formed smaller teams made of one to three researchers each focused on one module⁴. The teams were in charge of identifying the variables/concepts we aimed at measuring in each module and translating them into questions. For this phase we used some of the

⁴ The work of the thematic teams was organized and coordinated by Antonina Levatino. The teams working on the different thematic modules were the following: 1) Module “Enactment”: Marjolein Camphuijsen and Lluís Parcerisa; 2) Module: “Teacher Professionalism”: Natalie Brownes, Antonina Levatino and Marcel Pagès; 3) Module “LEM”: Andreu Termes; 4) Module “Global Education Industry”: Antoni Verger; 5) Module “Survey Experiments”: Antonina Levatino, Gerard Ferrer-Esteban and Antoni Verger; 6) Module “Pedagogical practices”: Gerard Ferrer-Esteban; 7) Module “School context”: Lluís Parcerisa.

recommendations given by Saris and Gallhofer (2014). The two researchers propose a three-step approach that allows to go from complex constructs, also named concepts-by-postulation (Blalock, 1990), to survey questions. The methodology constitutes an alternative to the common praxis of formulating questions directly from the variables one wants to measure. This latter practice has been found to lead to poor quality questions and measurement errors (Dillman, 2000).

Figure 2 presents an example on how we followed this methodology to transform the construct “attitude of towards performance-based accountability” into simpler and more measurable statements. As can be seen, in a first step, the methodology involves a deeper reflection on how to specify the complex constructs into simpler concepts. Afterwards, it implies an effort to transform these simpler concepts into assertions that indicates them. These assertions are then at the basis of the survey questions’ development.

Figure 2: Operationalization of the construct “Attitude toward performance-based accountability”

In order to improve the quality of the developed questions, we used Survey Quality predictor (SQP)⁵, a software that contains a coding system of survey items’ characteristics and predicts their reliability, validity and quality. The software provides information about the quality and comparative advantages of different question formats and gives suggestions to improve the design of survey questions. A part from using this feature of SQP, we also accessed its open source database to consult the way how some questions have been formulated and translated into different languages in other surveys.

⁵ For more information on SQP, see sqp.upf.edu

3.2 Experts' quality checks and development of Source Questionnaires

In October 2017, the drafts of the survey modules were sent out for critical review to an external panel made up of a number of academic experts⁶. As suggested by Presser and Blair (1994), this step can be considered an important first check of the quality of questionnaires' content. The external experts' consultation rounds lasted around 4 months. Afterwards, a first draft of the Source Questionnaires was formulated and submitted to a quality review by survey design experts of the Research and Expertise Centre for Survey Methodology (RECSM, Universitat Pompeu Fabra). This additional quality check, of a methodological nature, had the goal to avoid and minimise common pitfalls made by researchers when designing survey, especially in relation to double-barrelled and leading questions, unclear formulation of questions and incomplete or overlapping response categories.

The feedback was particularly determinant to help us making several decisions about the ordinal scales. As research has shown, designing these kinds of scales is particularly challenging as the number of scale characteristics can sensibly affect data quality (DeCastellarnau, 2018).

The scales in the REFORMED questionnaires are always either fully labelled or give at least the two end-points. Fixed reference points are thus always provided. These are verbal labels that standardise the scale and enhance comparability across respondents (Zavala-Rojas, 2014). The aim of these fixed anchors is to leave no doubt about the position of the points of the scale in the mind of the respondents (Saris and Gallhofer, 2014). Often, existing questionnaires (e.g. TALIS questionnaires) make use of uncertain quantifiers, such as "Much" or "A lot", as end-points of ordinal scales. However, these cannot be considered accurate anchors as they can have different meaning for different respondents, so the risk is that the respondents end up using different mental scales (Saris and De Rooij, 1988). In line with survey methodology research suggestions (DeCastellarnau, 2018), in the questionnaires, we use, for example, the words "Never" and "Always" as fixed anchors in objective temporal scales and "Not at all", "Absolutely", "Extremely" and "Completely" in subjective ones. Research has indeed shown that the use of such fixed anchors improves measurements' quality (Revilla and Ochoa, 2015). When possible, we also made an effort to develop questions with construct-specific response response-scales (Saris et al., 2010).

One of the most complex decisions we had to face regarding the scales' development concerned their lengths. As noted by DeCastellarnau (2018), this is one of the most difficult, and therefore most studied, issues in scales' development. No consensus has been reached on how many scales points are optimal (see e.g. Miethe, 1985; Alwin, 1997; Saris and Gallhofer, 2014). While too few categories can make it impossible to differentiate between respondents with different underlying opinions, too many categories can hamper the capacity of respondents to distinguish between them (Schaeffer and Presser, 2003; DeCastellarnau, 2018). As our questionnaires are long, we decided, following the advices of RECSM experts, to make use of scales with two different lengths in the questionnaires. This was in order to avoid response fatigue due to the monotony of the response options format. In the thinking aloud pre-testing phase, we provided some questions with five, seven and ten response scales options. We observed that with the longest scales, respondents showed problems in understanding the meaning of the different response options. We thus decided to use five- or seven- points ordinal scales. These are commonly used in survey design and have been recommended by several experts who studied the impact of scales lengths on measurement's quality (see, for example, Lundmark et al., 2016; Lozan et al., 2008; Preston and Colman, 2000; Krosnik and Fabrigar, 1997; Sherpenzeel and Saris, 1997). For Agree-Disagree rating scales we always use five-point scales as recent research has shown they yield data of better quality (Revilla et al., 2013). There are few exceptions to our decision to use five or seven point-scales. The first one concern the scales that aim at measuring the opinion on the fairness of PBA and the opinion on the value for money of services provided by private companies. In these two cases, we use a four-point scale that expands the original "Yes/No" categories so to offer the possibility to the respondent to report a more moderate or stronger opinion. No middle category is offered so the respondent is forced to give an opinion. The second exception concerns the Agree-Disagree scale we use to measure "teacher self-

⁶ A list of the academics that formed the experts' panel can be found in the Acknowledgements of this note.

efficacy”. For the measurement of this construct, we relied on an existing instrument (Hoy and Woolfolk, 1993). For comparability purposes, we thus decided to use the same response-categories (six) as in the original one.

Once the questions were modified according to the feedback of the experts, second versions of the Source Questionnaires were finalized. In this phase, we paid particular attention to how to order questions in the questionnaires. The goal was to minimize the “question order effect”, i.e. avoid that questions coming early in the questionnaire could affect the responses of subsequent questions (Miller, 2008; Oldendick, 2008). Also, we decided to place the most complex and relevant questions early in the questionnaire to maximize their likelihood of completion. However, as respondents may need some time to familiarize themselves with the questionnaire and reach their attention peak, in order to maximize the quality of the responses to the crucial questions, we made them be preceded by a few factual easy questions (for instance, basic demographic information and role covered in the school). The placement of these few questions at the very beginning of the questionnaires also ensures we have at least this basic information for cases where an early drop out from the Survey occurs. We finally left the majority of basic, factual questions at the end of the questionnaires, when attention typically drops and is easier for respondents to answer about facts (Anand, 2008; Holyk, 2008).

3.3 Adaptation, translation and national pre-testing

The Source Questionnaires were designed in English. Several substantive and linguistic cross-cultural annotations (coming from a set of consultations conducted with our partners in the participating countries) on how items and answer categories should be adapted to the national cases, accompanied it to help in the adaptation and translation phases. To achieve equivalence with regard to the translations, we were inspired by the TRAPD methodology, commonly used for the translation of the European Social Survey (European Social Survey, 2018). TRAPD is the acronym for Translation, Review, Adjudication, Pre-testing and Documentation (Harkness, 2003). In the REFORMED Project, for each country case, two translators were in charge to translate the questionnaires in an independent and parallel manner. When both versions of the translations were provided, the persons in charge of the translation met, eventually with a third person (the adjudicator), to discuss the translation and arrived to the first draft version of the translated questionnaires.

After having programmed the Survey using the Qualtrics platform, national pre-tests have been conducted with at least 4 respondents per case (2 principals and 2 teachers) using cognitive interviewing (Priede and Farrall, 2011). This is a qualitative methodology that asks participants to express their thoughts and opinions while reading and responding to a survey. The ultimate aim is to understand how potential respondents interpret and process survey questions to enhance standardisation and identify potential problems (Drennan, 2003). The technique we used was a mixture between concurrent thinking-aloud (Ericsson and Simon, 1993), verbal probing (Converse and Presser, 1986), complemented by a retrospective interview. A REFORMED Project researcher always accompanied the national pre-tests and instructed the respondent to verbalise their thoughts and opinions while completing the Survey. The researcher did not only take note of the respondent’s comments, but also of their non-verbal expressions and, either concurrently or retrospectively, interrogated them about their perplexities, doubts and interpretation, eventually asking them for suggestions for improvement.

These national pre-tests served several purposes. First, they helped to check whether questions were easily and generally understood in the same way by the target population as well as to make sure that this understanding was the one we intended. To ensure this, we also welcomed suggestions on how to rephrase or name some specific issues. The pre-tests also had the purpose to guarantee that potential respondents, across the different country-cases, gave the same meaning to the questions and consequently based their answers “on a common set of themes” (De Jongl et al., 2019: 129), so to strengthen the cross-case comparability of the Survey. Moreover, they served to identify missing answer categories and the need to introduce an “I don’t know” option as a necessary response category in some questions. Finally, they also aimed at checking for technical mistakes, improving Survey layout, measuring Survey length and fine-tuning.

4. Questionnaires' content

This section presents the content of REFORMED questionnaires in more detail. The presentation of the content does not reflect the order of different modules and questions in the questionnaires. The Source questionnaires in English with all the notations regarding filters and the adaptation to the REFORMED case studies are provided in the Appendix of this note.

4.1 SAWA enactment

Questions on enactment of SAWA policies constitute the core of the REFORMED Survey. As explained above, enactment is conceptually made up of two constitutive and interrelated moments: “interpretation”, which concerns perceptions and attitudes towards the policies, and “translation”, which regards the concrete practices.

Our aim is to investigate to what extent SAWA policies are enacted in different legal, institutional, socio-economic and professional settings. The data are also useful to explore the variegated ways in which SAWA policies are re-contextualized locally, and the “degree of congruence” (Coburn, 2001) between “policy, perceptions and actual practices” at school level.

In order to design the survey's questions on enactment, the REFORMED team conducted a thorough analysis of the OECD discourse on autonomy and accountability. From this analysis, Lluís Parcerisa, Andreu Termes and Antoni Verger derived a Theory of Change (ToC) behind SAWA policies (see Figure 3). Before specifically describing the content of the questions on enactment, it is thus relevant to have a look at the assumptions at the base of the ToC of SAWA policies.

Figure 3: Theory of Change behind SAWA policies

Source: Lluís Parcerisa, Andreu Termes and Antoni Verger (REFORMED team)

As implied by the figure, the ToC is based on several assumptions regarding test-based accountability, as well as autonomy:

- The locus of educational quality is located at the schools, principals, and teachers' levels.
- Students' learning outcomes are a core indicator of educational quality.
- External standardised tests constitute an adequate way to measure and evaluate students' learning and make a diagnosis that allows improving it.
- Incentives schemes of a different nature (material, symbolic, etc.) can foster teachers' motivation, efficiency and, ultimately, the quality of their teaching.
- These positive outcomes are particularly beneficial when accountability is combined with pedagogical and managerial autonomy.
- Pedagogical autonomy is assumed to generate relevant and locally adapted pedagogy in the framework of responsive schools. That is, standardised test results provide valuable information that can allow schools to adapt their practices to their local specificities.
- School pedagogical autonomy combined with PBA makes schools more responsive to students' needs and family preferences. At the aggregate level, this generates a more diversified educational environment, different from the bureaucratically limited "one-size-fits-all" pedagogy.
- Managerial autonomy allows principals to hire and fire teachers, which leads to more cohesive teams. Namely, the principal can fire those teachers who do not fit with the school's needs, educational project and mission.
- Because of their effect of enhancing teachers' capacity to adapt and create specific didactic approach and teaching materials and to create cohesive teams, pedagogical and managerial autonomy jointly increase teachers' job professional satisfaction and self-efficacy.

Based on the realist evaluation framework, our aim is to explore whether and to what extent the main assumptions on the benefits of SAWA policies, which are at the base of their wide diffusion, are perceived as those by teachers and principals and, whether and to what extent these expected benefits are supported by the empirical evidence. Beside this, we are also interested in potential side-effects of SAWA policies. As previous research has shown, educational accountability can lead to a number of negative, undesired effects, such as narrowing the curriculum, students' selection, teaching to the test and even cheating behaviours, because of the increased stress and pressure (Ohemeng and McCall-Thomas, 2013). Regarding autonomy, arguments have also raised against school autonomy, as one may argue that it could jeopardize access to an equal education and be detrimental for social and national cohesion (Cribb and Gewirtz, 2007).

In the following sub-sections, we will highlight the aspects of SAWA policies' interpretation and translation we aim to capture in the Survey, as well as present two survey experiments inserted in the questionnaires to explore SAWA side-effects.

4.1.1 SAWA policies' interpretation / Opinion and attitudes towards PBA and autonomy

According to Ball et al. (2012), policy is not translated directly from texts into practices. When teachers or other school-based actors are confronted with a new policy message or a new policy programme, they interpret and try to make sense of the related ideas, before putting them into practice (Coburn, 2001). Given that policy messages often reach schools in abstract nature (Coburn, 2001), the exploration of the process of interpretation becomes both necessary and unavoidable. Through the process of interpretation and sense-making, which are both individual and collective in nature, some policy ideas are adopted, adapted, and transformed, while others are ignored. Thus, principals' and teachers' views on accountability policies - which are probably contingent to their broader views on what is good quality education and to their professional identities and interests - play a key role to understand how these are re-contextualized in different educational settings. In an investigation carried out in three European countries, which include Finland, Ireland and Sweden, Müller and Hernández (2010) show that teachers perceive

accountability with scepticism. Similarly, in the U.S., Jones and Egley (2004) show how many teachers (79%) have negative perceptions of high-stakes testing, and these, in turn, have negative effects on teachers’ practices.

The exploration of this process of interpretation is not only needed to understand responses and policy translation into practices. It constitutes a research object in itself. Data collected through these questions can be used to explore the relation between school-specific factors as well as individual factors and different interpretations of SAWA policy messages. In particular, they make it possible to investigate to what extent the socioeconomic context of the school and the perception of competitive pressure coming from the LEM or the accountability system itself are related to particular interpretations of SAWA policies. A variable measuring the shared understanding of accountability policies within one school could be built and used to explore the role of context in the construction of shared understandings about the policy.

The following table shows the questions related with the process of interpretation of SAWA policies, as well as the variables/constructs we aim at measuring.

Table 2: Enactment-interpretation: variables and questions

CONSTRUCT/ VARIABLE	QUESTION WORDING	REMARKS	INSTR.
Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom	<p>To your knowledge, do the results of [national test] have any kind of consequences (economic, work-related, reputational, academic, etc.) for any of the following actors? (Multiple choice possible)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ For teachers ▪ For students ▪ For the school ▪ For Norwegian public schools: For the school owner ▪ For Norwegian private schools: For the school board ▪ For the NL: For the school board <p>X No consequences X I do not know</p>	In the Dutch case, we ask here about the eindtoets only (for comparability reasons).	PQ & TQ
Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – what consequences for principals	<p>What are the consequences of the [national test]? (Multiple choice possible)</p> <p>FOR THE PRINCIPAL:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Salary bonus ▪ Increases or decreases of salary ▪ The principal can be withdrawn from his/her position ▪ Impact on professional reputation ▪ Other, please specify: ___ <p>X I do not know the exact consequences</p>	In the Dutch case, we ask here about the eindtoets only (for comparability reasons).	PQ & TQ
Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – what consequences for teachers	<p>What are the consequences of the [national test]? (Multiple choice possible)</p> <p>FOR TEACHERS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Salary bonus ▪ Increases or decreases of salary ▪ Provision of professional development (training and attendance to conferences, mentoring, individual/collaborative research) ▪ Teachers’ tenure/promotion decisions ▪ Impact on professional reputation ▪ Other, please specify: ___ <p>X I do not know the exact consequences</p>	In the Dutch case, we ask here about the eindtoets only (for comparability reasons).	PQ & TQ

<p>Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – what consequences for students</p>	<p>What are the consequences of the [national test]? <i>(Multiple choice possible)</i></p> <p>FOR STUDENTS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Student grade promotion or graduation ▪ Rewards for students ▪ Other, please specify: ____ <p>X I do not know the exact consequences</p>	<p>In the Dutch case, we ask here about the eindtoets only (for comparability reasons).</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>
<p>Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – what consequences for the school</p>	<p>What are the consequences of the [national test]? <i>(Multiple choice possible)</i></p> <p>FOR THE SCHOOL:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>For Chile:</i> The school is more closely monitored by the ministry ▪ School closure ▪ <i>All cases, except Norway:</i> Award of a collective salary bonus ▪ Impact on the school reputation ▪ The educational authority provides extra support/resources to the school ▪ <i>All cases, except Norway and Chile:</i> The school is more closely monitored by the inspectorate ▪ <i>For Chile:</i> The school is more closely monitored by the Agency of Quality ▪ <i>For Norway:</i> The school is more closely monitored by the [school owner/school board] ▪ <i>For the NL:</i> The school is more closely monitored by the school board ▪ Other, please specify: ____ <p>X I do not know the exact consequences</p>	<p>In the Dutch case, we ask here about the eindtoets only (for comparability reasons).</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>
<p>Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – what consequences for the school board</p>	<p>What are the consequences of the [national test]? <i>(Multiple choice possible)</i></p> <p>FOR THE SCHOOL BOARD:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The school board is more closely monitored by the ministry ▪ The school board is more closely monitored by the inspectorate ▪ Other, please specify: ____ <p>X I do not know the exact consequences</p>	<p>This question applies only to the Dutch case. We ask here about the eindtoets only (for comparability reasons).</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>
<p>Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – what consequences for the school owner</p>	<p>What are the consequences of the [national test]?</p> <p>FOR THE SCHOOL OWNER: Please indicate here the consequences the [national test] can have for the school owner: _____</p>	<p>This question applies only to Norwegian public schools.</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>
<p>Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – what consequences for the school board</p>	<p>What are the consequences of the [national test]?</p> <p>FOR THE SCHOOL BOARD: Please indicate here the consequences the [national test] can have for the school owner: _____</p>	<p>This question applies only to Norwegian private schools.</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>
<p>Opinion on the causal effects of PBA – effect on school reputation</p>	<p>Do you think that a school's [national test] results influence its reputation?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Absolutely ○ A lot ○ To some extent ○ A little ○ Not at all 	<p>In the Dutch case, we ask here about the eindtoets only (for comparability reasons).</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>

<p>Opinion on the causal effects of PBA – effect on competition between teachers</p>	<p>Do you think it is important for teachers in this school that their students outperform those of other classes in the [national test]? <i>Please consider both other classes of the same grades and of different grades.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Absolutely ☐ A lot ☐ To some extent ☐ A little ☐ Not at all 	<p>In the Dutch case, we ask here both tests jointly.</p>	<p>TQ</p>				
<p>Opinion on fairness of PBA</p>	<p>To what extent do you think that it is fair...</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="496 591 1142 898"> <tr> <td data-bbox="496 591 815 680"> <p>... to measure the quality of a school based on [national test] results?</p> </td> <td data-bbox="815 591 1142 898" rowspan="3"> <p>For each question:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Very fair ☐ Fair ☐ Unfair ☐ Very unfair </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="496 680 815 770"> <p>... to publicly disseminate [national test] results in the media and/or internet?</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="496 770 815 898"> <p>... that schools with different characteristics are compared on the basis of their [national test] results?</p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p>... to measure the quality of a school based on [national test] results?</p>	<p>For each question:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Very fair ☐ Fair ☐ Unfair ☐ Very unfair 	<p>... to publicly disseminate [national test] results in the media and/or internet?</p>	<p>... that schools with different characteristics are compared on the basis of their [national test] results?</p>	<p>In the Dutch case, we ask here about the eindtoets only (for comparability reasons).</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>
<p>... to measure the quality of a school based on [national test] results?</p>	<p>For each question:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Very fair ☐ Fair ☐ Unfair ☐ Very unfair 						
<p>... to publicly disseminate [national test] results in the media and/or internet?</p>							
<p>... that schools with different characteristics are compared on the basis of their [national test] results?</p>							
<p>Opinion on the validity of the test</p>	<p>In your opinion, to what extent do a school's scores in [national test] reflect the efforts and ability of the individual teachers?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Completely ☐ A lot ☐ Some ☐ A little ☐ Not at all <p>To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="496 1263 1142 1570"> <tr> <td data-bbox="496 1263 799 1352"> <p>A good teacher can be recognized by his/her students' results in [national test]</p> </td> <td data-bbox="799 1263 1142 1570" rowspan="2"> <p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly agree ☐ Agree ☐ Neither agree nor disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Strongly disagree </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="496 1352 799 1570"> <p>The results of [national test] do not adequately represent what students have learned and can do</p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p>A good teacher can be recognized by his/her students' results in [national test]</p>	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly agree ☐ Agree ☐ Neither agree nor disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Strongly disagree 	<p>The results of [national test] do not adequately represent what students have learned and can do</p>	<p>In the Dutch case, we ask here about the eindtoets only (for comparability reasons).</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>	
<p>A good teacher can be recognized by his/her students' results in [national test]</p>	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly agree ☐ Agree ☐ Neither agree nor disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Strongly disagree 						
<p>The results of [national test] do not adequately represent what students have learned and can do</p>							
<p>Opinion on the usefulness of the test</p>	<p>To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="496 1659 1142 1966"> <tr> <td data-bbox="496 1659 799 1783"> <p>Preparation for [national test] takes too much time away from more important activities in school</p> </td> <td data-bbox="799 1659 1142 1966" rowspan="3"> <p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly agree ☐ Agree ☐ Neither agree nor disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Strongly disagree </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="496 1783 799 1872"> <p>The content of [national test] tells us what the school's priorities are</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="496 1872 799 1966"> <p>The results of [national test] do not provide useful information on student learning</p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p>Preparation for [national test] takes too much time away from more important activities in school</p>	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly agree ☐ Agree ☐ Neither agree nor disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Strongly disagree 	<p>The content of [national test] tells us what the school's priorities are</p>	<p>The results of [national test] do not provide useful information on student learning</p>	<p>In the Dutch case, we ask here about the eindtoets only (for comparability reasons).</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>
<p>Preparation for [national test] takes too much time away from more important activities in school</p>	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly agree ☐ Agree ☐ Neither agree nor disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Strongly disagree 						
<p>The content of [national test] tells us what the school's priorities are</p>							
<p>The results of [national test] do not provide useful information on student learning</p>							

<p>Perception of pressure from PBA</p>	<p><i>In the PQ: How much pressure do you, as the {Piped text with leadership function in the school} in this school, feel to get good results in the [national test]?</i></p> <p><i>In the TQ (for teachers who are preparing or ever prepared student for the test): How much pressure do you feel to get good results in [national test]?</i></p> <p><i>In the TQ (for teachers who have never prepared student for the test): How much pressure do teachers feel to get good results in [national test]?</i></p> <p><i>Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "None at all" and 7 indicates "An extreme amount".</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ 7 An extreme amount ☐ 6 ☐ 5 ☐ 4 ☐ 3 ☐ 2 ☐ 1 None at all 	<p>In the Dutch case, we ask firstly about the eindtoets (for comparability reasons). Afterwards, we repeat the questions to ask about the LVS-tests.</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>																		
<p>Perception of pressure from PBA - Pressuring actors</p>	<p>To what extent does this pressure come from the following actors?</p> <p><i>Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all" and 7 indicates "Extremely".</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="496 992 1142 1740"> <tr> <td>Ministry of Education – Federal/Central authority</td> <td rowspan="14"> <p>For each option:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ 7 An extreme amount ☐ 6 ☐ 5 ☐ 4 ☐ 3 ☐ 2 ☐ 1 None at all </td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>For Chile:</i> Agency of Quality</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>For Chile:</i> "Superintendence"</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>For Norway:</i> Regional Authority</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>For the Spanish cases:</i> Autonomic authority</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>For Chilean public schools, Norway and the NL:</i> Municipal authority</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>For the NL:</i> School board</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>For the NL and the Spanish cases:</i> The inspectorate</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>For not public schools, except for the NL:</i> School board</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>In the TQ:</i> Principal and/or other members of the leadership team</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>In Chile and the Spanish cases:</i> School council</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>In the PQ:</i> Teachers</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>In the TQ:</i> Other teachers</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Parents</td> </tr> <tr> <td>The media</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Self-imposed pressure</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other, please specify: ____</td> </tr> </table>	Ministry of Education – Federal/Central authority	<p>For each option:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ 7 An extreme amount ☐ 6 ☐ 5 ☐ 4 ☐ 3 ☐ 2 ☐ 1 None at all 	<i>For Chile:</i> Agency of Quality	<i>For Chile:</i> "Superintendence"	<i>For Norway:</i> Regional Authority	<i>For the Spanish cases:</i> Autonomic authority	<i>For Chilean public schools, Norway and the NL:</i> Municipal authority	<i>For the NL:</i> School board	<i>For the NL and the Spanish cases:</i> The inspectorate	<i>For not public schools, except for the NL:</i> School board	<i>In the TQ:</i> Principal and/or other members of the leadership team	<i>In Chile and the Spanish cases:</i> School council	<i>In the PQ:</i> Teachers	<i>In the TQ:</i> Other teachers	Parents	The media	Self-imposed pressure	Other, please specify: ____	<p>In the Dutch case, we ask firstly about the eindtoets (for comparability reasons). Afterwards, we repeat the questions to ask about the LVS-tests.</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>
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Parents																					
The media																					
Self-imposed pressure																					
Other, please specify: ____																					

<p>Preferences on school autonomy and decision-making</p>	<p>In your opinion, for a school to work well, who should be responsible of the following domains? (Multiple choice possible)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="496 344 1144 1077"> <tr> <td data-bbox="496 344 815 1077"> <p>Budget allocation Selection of school principals Selection of new teachers <i>All cases, except Norway:</i> Teachers' salary increases/Teachers' promotion <i>All cases, except Norway:</i> Students' admission into the school <i>All cases, except the NL:</i> Curriculum adjustment (curricular objectives and/or content) <i>For the NL:</i> Curriculum development Choice of textbooks and teaching materials Content of in-service training Assessment of teaching quality Teaching methods Students' assessment criteria and procedures <i>For the NL:</i> Choice of eindtoets <i>For the NL:</i> Choice of LVS The raising and use of private funds</p> </td> <td data-bbox="823 344 1144 1077"> <p>Educational authorities/administration Principal and/or leadership team <i>All cases, except Norway and the NL:</i> School council <i>For the NL:</i> Medezeggenschapsraad Teachers</p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p>Budget allocation Selection of school principals Selection of new teachers <i>All cases, except Norway:</i> Teachers' salary increases/Teachers' promotion <i>All cases, except Norway:</i> Students' admission into the school <i>All cases, except the NL:</i> Curriculum adjustment (curricular objectives and/or content) <i>For the NL:</i> Curriculum development Choice of textbooks and teaching materials Content of in-service training Assessment of teaching quality Teaching methods Students' assessment criteria and procedures <i>For the NL:</i> Choice of eindtoets <i>For the NL:</i> Choice of LVS The raising and use of private funds</p>	<p>Educational authorities/administration Principal and/or leadership team <i>All cases, except Norway and the NL:</i> School council <i>For the NL:</i> Medezeggenschapsraad Teachers</p>		<p>PQ & TQ</p>
<p>Budget allocation Selection of school principals Selection of new teachers <i>All cases, except Norway:</i> Teachers' salary increases/Teachers' promotion <i>All cases, except Norway:</i> Students' admission into the school <i>All cases, except the NL:</i> Curriculum adjustment (curricular objectives and/or content) <i>For the NL:</i> Curriculum development Choice of textbooks and teaching materials Content of in-service training Assessment of teaching quality Teaching methods Students' assessment criteria and procedures <i>For the NL:</i> Choice of eindtoets <i>For the NL:</i> Choice of LVS The raising and use of private funds</p>	<p>Educational authorities/administration Principal and/or leadership team <i>All cases, except Norway and the NL:</i> School council <i>For the NL:</i> Medezeggenschapsraad Teachers</p>				
<p>Subjective perception of centrality of national test in the public educational debate</p>	<p>In your opinion, how much importance is given to the [national test] in the current public educational debate?</p> <p>Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all important" and 7 indicates "Extremely important".</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ 7 Extremely important ☐ 6 ☐ 5 ☐ 4 ☐ 3 ☐ 2 ☐ 1 Not at all important 	<p>In the Dutch case, we ask here about the eindtoets only (for comparability reasons).</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>		

As can be seen in the Table 2, three different dimensions are of particular interest here. The first one concerns respondents' knowledge of the accountability regime and familiarity with accountability mechanisms. We believe that collecting information on the knowledge of the policies by the respondents is crucial. Indeed, exploring opinions and beliefs about SAWA policies, as well as responses, without checking *what the respondents know* about the policies could generate biases. Compared to the objective consequences that are consultable in secondary sources, asking school actors about their knowledge of the consequences is more accurate information in order to know to what extent the consequences at stake may impact actors' behaviour. Furthermore, matching respondents' answers to secondary data give us also information on school actors' level of knowledge of accountability policies. The second dimension concerns attitudes towards SAWA policies. On this, a wide range of questions are included in the questionnaires. Questions on opinions on the validity of the standardised tests are included to capture to what extent the national test is considered as a valid instrument to measure students' performance and teachers' work. To explore whether teachers and principals consider the national standardised assessment as a fair gauge of school quality and individual teachers' performance, we add questions exploring opinions on the fairness of the

accountability system. Questions asking about the opinions on the usefulness of the national test are added in order to capture whether the respondents perceive it as a useful tool to provide a focus for instruction. Questions on beliefs of PBA causal effects are also included. A further dimension concerns teachers' and principals' perceptions of pressure related to PBA. This allows exploring whether and how perceived pressure vary according to the design of SAWA policies and to the school context where the policies are enacted. Finally, in the attempt to understand respondents' attitudes towards autonomy, we ask a question about preferences on school autonomy, by interrogating the respondents about who should be involved in the decision-making in several relevant domains.

It should be pointed out that a range of difficulties are attached to studying the process of interpretation. The first challenge relates to the same nature of the process. Interpretation is indeed a highly iterative and recursive process. Coburn (2001: 156) found that "teachers returned to issues over and over throughout the year, modifying their interpretations, reconsidering technical and practical concerns, and often making new gatekeeping decisions as they came into contact with additional messages from the environment or experimented with new approaches or materials in their classrooms". This means that measuring school-based actors' interpretations of a new policy message at one moment in time presents a shortcoming that should be taken into account because it may not be sufficient to fully explain why certain policy messages are adopted, transformed, rejected, and result in a range of different responses. The second challenge relates to measuring the process of interpretation in a quantitative manner. As school-based actors are simultaneously confronted with a range of different policy messages at the same time, it becomes difficult to disentangle attitudes towards a particular policy. In the REFORMED Project we attempt to do so. Nonetheless, the majority of studies examining the process of policy interpretation (and more broadly, policy enactment) have done so in a qualitative manner (see Ball, et al. 2012; Braun, et al. 2010; Coburn, 2001; 2005). Consequently, the REFORMED Project had limited examples of other surveys to build on (e.g. Jones and Egley, 2004). This part of the Survey constitutes a genuine contribution of the Project with the uncertainty attached to pioneering work. Notwithstanding these difficulties, we consider that it is both relevant and necessary to study this process in a quantitative manner. A quantitative approach can provide evidence of how individual characteristics as well as the micro-institutional and socioeconomic contexts can be related to different understandings of SAWA policies.

4.1.2 SAWA policies' translation / Use of national standardised tests

According to the above-mentioned ToC, SAWA policies are expected to foster relevant education, innovation and team cohesion. Regarding the effects of SAWA policies on learning outcomes, research is inconclusive (Verger and Parcerisa, 2015). Some researchers have found positive effects of accountability measures on learning achievement (Chiang 2009). Negative effects of accountability, such as narrowing the curriculum or curriculum alignment, i.e. adapting the curriculum to the content of the tests, have been also identified (Rothstein et al., 2008; Jones and Egley, 2004). These latter seem to be particularly present in high stakes environments because of the increased accountability pressures (Darling-Hammond, 2004; Verger and Parcerisa, 2017). In the REFORMED Project, we define these kinds of practices as "instrumental", because they are thought as instruments for reaching concrete goals, some of these clearly linked to test-based accountability. Instrumental practices are for us the opposite of "expressive" practices that are aimed at assuring a meaningful pedagogical experience. A part from questions asking about curriculum narrowing, curriculum alignment and teaching to the test, we ask questions about pedagogical approach. More specifically, we include questions asking about different types of teaching methods (transmissive, frontal, content-based vs. interactive teaching) and questions related with the process of learning (metacognitive, feedback and group work). These questions might be also used to create profiles of teachers.

Finally, we collect information on whether and to what extent principals and teachers use data coming from national standardised tests and what the main challenges connected to this use are. In almost every case covered by the REFORMED Project, it is possible to identify clear institutional expectations regarding the use of national test

results⁷. Schools are commonly asked to analyse and discuss them to get relevant information about the school; to develop an improvement plan based on the results of the test; to adapt the pedagogical plan on the basis of the diagnostic coming from the data results; and to practice tests and apply test-friendly evaluation system. It is however not known how intensively test data are really used, or how they are being combined with other sources of data for educational improvement purposes. Identifying the difficulties faced by teachers and principals in interpreting and using national test data also seems crucial. In the Norwegian case, for example, Gunnulfson (2018) found that even though the interviewed teachers had positive attitudes towards the national standardized test, it had a limited impact on their instruction methods because they did not have the ability to interpret test results and received too little support to do so.

The following table displays the variables/constructs related with the process of translation of SAWA policies we aim at measuring in our questionnaires.

Table 3: Enactment-translation: variables and questions

CONSTRUCT/ VARIABLE	QUESTION WORDING	REMARKS	INSTR.					
Attention to diversity	<p>On average, how often do you do the following in your class?</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>I create groups of students with similar abilities</td> <td rowspan="4"> For each statement: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ IN EVERY CLASS ○ FREQUENTLY (several times a week) ○ OCCASIONALLY (several times a month) ○ SELDOM (once a month) ○ NEVER </td> </tr> <tr> <td>I create groups with mixed abilities</td> </tr> <tr> <td>I give different work to the students who have learning difficulties</td> </tr> <tr> <td>I give different work to the advanced students</td> </tr> </table>	I create groups of students with similar abilities	For each statement: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ IN EVERY CLASS ○ FREQUENTLY (several times a week) ○ OCCASIONALLY (several times a month) ○ SELDOM (once a month) ○ NEVER 	I create groups with mixed abilities	I give different work to the students who have learning difficulties	I give different work to the advanced students		TQ
I create groups of students with similar abilities	For each statement: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ IN EVERY CLASS ○ FREQUENTLY (several times a week) ○ OCCASIONALLY (several times a month) ○ SELDOM (once a month) ○ NEVER 							
I create groups with mixed abilities								
I give different work to the students who have learning difficulties								
I give different work to the advanced students								
Access to individual test data	<p>Do you have access to your students' individual scores on the [national test]?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Yes ○ No 		TQ					
Capacity to use national test data	<p>In this school do you consider it difficult to transform national test data into concrete measures/actions to improve teaching?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Absolutely ○ A lot ○ To some extent ○ A little ○ Not at all 	In the Dutch case, here we ask about the eindtoets (because we want to compare with other cases).	PQ & TQ					

⁷ A notable exception seems to be the Dutch case where schools seem to have more autonomy regarding the use of data coming from the national test.

<p>Change of resources distribution</p>	<p><i>All cases, except Norway:</i> In your school has [national test] led to a redistribution of resources (time, personnel, and budget) in favour of the subject areas and competences that are tested?</p> <p><i>For Norway:</i> In your school has [national test] led to a redistribution of resources (time, personnel, and budget) in favour of competences that are tested?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Completely ☐ A lot ☐ Some ☐ A little ☐ Not at all 		<p>PQ & TQ</p>							
<p>Curriculum narrowing</p>	<p>In your school, to what extent is [national test] taken into account when taking decisions about curricular content?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Completely ☐ A lot ☐ Some ☐ A little ☐ None at all 		<p>PQ & TQ</p>							
<p>Educational approaches and teaching practices</p>	<p>How often does each of the following happen in your class throughout the school year? <i>Please mark one choice in each row.</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="440 1043 1094 1541"> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 1043 703 1137">I explicitly state the learning goals at the beginning of the activities</td> <td data-bbox="703 1043 1094 1541" rowspan="6"> <p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ IN EVERY CLASS ☐ FREQUENTLY (several times a week) ☐ OCCASIONALLY (several times a month) ☐ SELDOM (once a month) ☐ NEVER </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 1137 703 1200">I present a summary of recently learned content</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 1200 703 1294">I present the lesson units in an organized and sequenced manner</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 1294 703 1357">I ask questions to check students' understanding</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 1357 703 1451">I check students' exercise books or homework and provide feedback</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 1451 703 1541">I provide feedback during class about how students are working</td> </tr> </table>	I explicitly state the learning goals at the beginning of the activities	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ IN EVERY CLASS ☐ FREQUENTLY (several times a week) ☐ OCCASIONALLY (several times a month) ☐ SELDOM (once a month) ☐ NEVER 	I present a summary of recently learned content	I present the lesson units in an organized and sequenced manner	I ask questions to check students' understanding	I check students' exercise books or homework and provide feedback	I provide feedback during class about how students are working		<p>TQ</p>
I explicitly state the learning goals at the beginning of the activities	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ IN EVERY CLASS ☐ FREQUENTLY (several times a week) ☐ OCCASIONALLY (several times a month) ☐ SELDOM (once a month) ☐ NEVER 									
I present a summary of recently learned content										
I present the lesson units in an organized and sequenced manner										
I ask questions to check students' understanding										
I check students' exercise books or homework and provide feedback										
I provide feedback during class about how students are working										
<p>Experience with the test - Currently preparing for the test</p>	<p>This school year, are you teaching a grade-level that will take/has taken part in the [national test]?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Yes ☐ No 	<p>In the Dutch case, here we ask about eindtoets.</p>	<p>TQ</p>							
<p>Experience with the test - Ever prepared students for the test</p>	<p>In the past, have you ever taught a grade-level that took part in the [national test]?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Yes ☐ No 	<p>In the Dutch case, here we ask about eindtoets.</p>	<p>TQ</p>							

<p>General teaching and learning methods</p>	<p>On average, how often do you do the following when you teach?</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="440 282 1075 618"> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 282 711 344">Students are given a lecture-style presentation</td> <td data-bbox="716 282 1075 618" rowspan="5"> <p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ IN EVERY CLASS ☐ FREQUENTLY (several times a week) ☐ OCCASIONALLY (several times a month) ☐ SELDOM (once a month) ☐ NEVER </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 344 711 383">Students work individually</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 383 711 412">Students work in groups</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 412 711 472">Students complete a test or quiz</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 472 711 618">Students are involved in debates and discussions</td> </tr> </table>	Students are given a lecture-style presentation	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ IN EVERY CLASS ☐ FREQUENTLY (several times a week) ☐ OCCASIONALLY (several times a month) ☐ SELDOM (once a month) ☐ NEVER 	Students work individually	Students work in groups	Students complete a test or quiz	Students are involved in debates and discussions		<p>TQ</p>
Students are given a lecture-style presentation	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ IN EVERY CLASS ☐ FREQUENTLY (several times a week) ☐ OCCASIONALLY (several times a month) ☐ SELDOM (once a month) ☐ NEVER 								
Students work individually									
Students work in groups									
Students complete a test or quiz									
Students are involved in debates and discussions									
<p>Influence on pedagogy</p>	<p>To what extent has the existence of learning standards influenced the pedagogical approach of this school?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Completely ☐ A lot ☐ Some ☐ A little ☐ None at all 		<p>PQ & TQ</p>						
<p>Instruction to adjust teaching to the test</p>	<p>In PQ: Has the [school owner or school board] recommended or instructed that teaching should be adjusted to the achievement of the evaluable learning standards?</p> <p>In TQ: Have the principal and the management team recommended and/or instructed that teaching should be more adjusted to the achievement of the evaluable learning standards?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Yes, it has been instructed ☐ Yes, it has been recommended ☐ No, never 	<p>In the PQ [school owner or school board] will be always school board in the NL. In the other cases this will depend on the provider. In the NL, we ask here also about the LVS in separate questions.</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>						
<p>Instruction to practice for the test</p>	<p>In PQ: Has the [school owner or school board] recommended or instructed that students should practice for [national test]?</p> <p>In TQ: Have the principal and the management team recommended and/or instructed that students should practice for [national test]?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Yes, it has been instructed ☐ Yes, it has been recommended ☐ No, never 	<p>In the PQ [school owner or school board] will be always school board in the NL. In the other cases this will depend on the provider. In the NL, we ask here also about the LVS in separate questions.</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>						
<p>Pedagogical practices</p>	<p>How often does each of the following happen in your class throughout the school year? <i>Please mark one choice in each row.</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="440 1812 1075 2083"> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 1812 711 1906">I encourage students to solve problems in more than one way</td> <td data-bbox="716 1812 1075 2083" rowspan="3"> <p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ IN EVERY CLASS ☐ FREQUENTLY (several times a week) ☐ OCCASIONALLY (several times a month) </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 1906 711 2029">I expect students to decide and explain their own procedures for solving complex problems</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="440 2029 711 2083">I ask students to relate what they are learning to</td> </tr> </table>	I encourage students to solve problems in more than one way	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ IN EVERY CLASS ☐ FREQUENTLY (several times a week) ☐ OCCASIONALLY (several times a month) 	I expect students to decide and explain their own procedures for solving complex problems	I ask students to relate what they are learning to		<p>TQ</p>		
I encourage students to solve problems in more than one way	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ IN EVERY CLASS ☐ FREQUENTLY (several times a week) ☐ OCCASIONALLY (several times a month) 								
I expect students to decide and explain their own procedures for solving complex problems									
I ask students to relate what they are learning to									

	<p>problems from daily life</p> <p>I ask students to explicitly think about and explain what they are learning</p> <p>Students work on projects that require at least one week to complete</p> <p>Students work in groups to come up with a joint solution to a problem or task</p> <p>Students use ICT (information and communication technology) for projects or class work</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SELDOM (once a month) ○ NEVER 		
Reasons for difficulties in using national test data	<p>What factors could explain these difficulties?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The interpretation of the data requires statistical competences ▪ Data are not provided at the student level ▪ Data do tell me anything I did not know before ▪ The report is not clear ▪ Lack of time to analyse/use the data ▪ Data/the report are not accessible ▪ Other, please specify: _____ 		In the Dutch case, here we ask about the eindtoets (because we want to compare with other cases).	PQ & TQ
Role of school inspector with the test	<p>The role of school inspectors regarding the [national test] is centred on: (Multiple answer possible)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Supervising the application of the school targets/plan ▪ Giving information about test implementation procedures ▪ For the NL: Delivering the LVS school results to the schools ▪ For the NL: Delivering the eindtoets school results to the schools ▪ For all cases, except the NL: Delivering the results of the [national test] to the schools ▪ Giving advice on how to strengthen the school performance in [national test] ▪ Observing teaching and giving feedback ▪ Other, please specify: __ 		This question applies to all cases, except Norway and Spanish private schools.	PQ
Use of national test	<p>In your school, what are the results of [national test] used for? (Multiple choice possible)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ To define and monitor our school improvement plan ▪ To identify students with a need for more support and follow-up ▪ To assess teachers' work ▪ To take decisions about professional development activities for teachers ▪ To inform parents about the school achievement ▪ To group students (by achievement) for instructional purposes ▪ To reward well-performing teachers ▪ To compare our performance with that of other schools ▪ To adjust the curriculum accordingly ▪ For Norway: To report among the teaching staff ▪ For the NL and Spanish secondary schools: To help stream students into further education ▪ To build school reputation 		In the NL we ask for both eindtoets and LVS separately.	PQ & TQ

Teaching to the test	<p>Do you conduct activities with your students that focus on preparing them for [national test] (such as practicing on previous tests/example questions, etc.)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Yes, during the whole year ☐ Yes, but only during the month before the test ☐ No, never 	In the Dutch case, questions on teaching to the test are asked separately for eindtoets and LVS-tests	TQ				
Teaching to the test – Frequency (if during the whole year)	<p>How often do you conduct activities with your students that focus on preparing them for [national test] (such as practicing on previous tests/example questions, etc.)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ In every class ☐ Frequently (several times a week) ☐ Occasionally (several times a month) ☐ Seldom (once a month) 		TQ				
Teaching to the test – Frequency (if during the month before the test)	<p>...during the month before the test?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ In every class ☐ Several times a week ☐ Once a week ☐ Once or twice 		TQ				
Training to use national test data	<p>Have you ever participated in any training activities focusing on how to analyse and use national test results for school improvement purposes?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Yes ☐ No 		PQ				
Workload increase because of the test (both LVS and eindtoets)	<p>Does your workload increase during testing periods (before and after the tests)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Yes ☐ No ☐ I have never taught a group that takes the eindtoets or LVS-tests 	This question applies only to the Dutch case.	TQ				
Workload increase - reasons	<p>To what extent does your workload increase because of:</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;">the increase of administrative tasks and paperwork?</td> <td rowspan="3"> For each question: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Absolutely ☐ A lot ☐ Some ☐ A little ☐ Not at all </td> </tr> <tr> <td>the increase of administrative tasks and paperwork?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>the increase in your teaching hours?</td> </tr> </table>	the increase of administrative tasks and paperwork?	For each question: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Absolutely ☐ A lot ☐ Some ☐ A little ☐ Not at all 	the increase of administrative tasks and paperwork?	the increase in your teaching hours?	This question applies only to the Dutch case.	TQ
the increase of administrative tasks and paperwork?	For each question: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Absolutely ☐ A lot ☐ Some ☐ A little ☐ Not at all 						
the increase of administrative tasks and paperwork?							
the increase in your teaching hours?							

4.1.3 Undesired effects of PBA: an experimental approach

Research has shown how accountability policies may encourage a wide range of practices, so-called opportunistic behaviours, on the part of schools, principals and teachers to maximise test-results. These behaviours, also commonly referred to as side-effects of accountability, include test-cheating (Jacob and Levitt, 2003; Ehren and Swanborn, 2012; Berliner, 2011), and cream-skimming, i.e. principals try to enrol students who are expected to perform better in the tests (Jennings, 2010). Evidently, these kinds of behaviours are undesired, and direct reporting about them may be subject to social desirability bias (Steiner et al., 2016). The sensitivity of the topics addressed is one of the reasons why we decided to explore them through survey experiments. Survey experiments indeed have proved to be able to effectively limit social desirability bias (Wallander, 2009).

Literature on accountability in education tends to differentiate between high-stakes and low-stakes accountability modalities. High-stakes accountability systems imply more intense consequences (rewards and/or sanctions) for the account-givers and are, therefore, often assumed to have a bigger impact on educational and organisational practices, as well as more likely to generate undesired practices. Nonetheless, recent research has revealed that, low-stakes accountability policies generate similar effects to those of high-stakes accountability (Thiel et al., 2017). This may be partly due to the reputational effect of accountability (Busoioc and Lodge, 2016). Existing studies on opportunistic behaviours in education has not yet been able to establish what the causal mechanism that explains the emergence of these undesired school responses is. Existing research usually involves investigations with a small sample that explore a specific context and do not have a control group to carry out a counterfactual analysis (see, for example, Jones and Egley, 2014). Lacking a counterfactual, it is not possible to establish whether opportunistic behaviour is due to the particular consequence associated with the test or due to the mere existence of a test. Similarly, it is not possible to know if someone who ‘fabricated’ test results would not have done it had the consequences attached to test results been different. Compared with observational studies, the experimental design has clear advantages regarding the analysis of causal effects (Holland, 1986).

The REFORMED Survey contains two experiments aiming at exploring two side-effects of accountability. The first one is a vignette experiment included in the TQ; the second one is a conjoint experiment inserted in the PQ.

With the vignette experiment we aim at answering at the following research questions: Is ‘cheating’ more likely when higher stakes are at stake? More specifically, to what extent can the consequences associated with standardized tests have a different effect on the generation of opportunistic behaviours? Are opportunistic behaviours subject to social desirability bias? In vignette experiments, each participant is randomly treated with a hypothetical situation that systematically presents different characteristics with regard to other possible situations (Atzmüller and Steiner, 2010). In our experiment, each respondent, randomly assigned to a group, reads a vignette that describes the situation of a teacher to whom a colleague advises ‘cheating’ in the context of a new national assessment, as a way to obtain better results in the test. The vignette is manipulated with regard to the possible consequences that the test may have if students obtain poor results. Some characteristics of the protagonist (gender) of the vignette, as well as the school composition where he or she teaches (middle class or vulnerable neighbourhood) are also randomly manipulated to ensure that these elements are not left to the imagination of the respondent, thus preventing the results to be influenced by these factors. At the end of the vignette, the respondent rates both the likelihood of the protagonist of the vignette to cheat and the likelihood of doing so if he/she personally were in the same situation. Belonging to the different experimental conditions does not depend on individual characteristics of the participant, but on a systematic random assignment. This makes the groups identical on average, except for the stimuli provided to their experimental groups (Druckman and Leeper, 2012). Because of this, differences in the group answers given to the follow-up questions can be attributed to the stimulus received. Box 1 presents the different variants of our vignette experiment as well as the follow-up questions⁸.

⁸ In the Norwegian case, the Survey was sent out per e-mail and self-administered, whereas, in the Netherlands, school actors experience a high level of fatigue due to the large number of surveys, which are regularly administered in Dutch schools. As both situations might lead to higher drop-out rates, we decided to exclude the vignette experiment from Norwegian and Dutch versions of the Survey. The inclusion of the vignette experiment causes the progress bar to advance slower and this could discourage respondents to continue to answer. This is obviously less relevant in contexts with less fatigue among school actors, but also when a surveyor assists the respondents while answering the Survey. In fact, the incidence of the online administration (vs. face-to-face) is significant in the completion rate, since we have seen that the probability of teachers to complete the questionnaire with assisted administration is between 5 and 6 times higher than with online administration.

Box 1: Vignette (TQ)

[Female/male typical name] is a teacher working at a school in a [vulnerable/middle-class] neighbourhood of Santiago.

Next week a new national test, already implemented in other countries, will be conducted for the first time in the grade in which María teaches.

For [name of the teacher] is very important that her students get good results in the test.

BASELINE CONDITION/CONTROL: [-]

TREATMENT 1: In case of bad test results, the school owner will reduce the funding given to [name of the teacher]'s school.

TREATMENT 2: In case of bad test results, [name of the teacher] will stop receiving her salary bonus.

TREATMENT 3: In case of bad test results, [name of the teacher]'s school reputation will be damaged by the publication of the results in the media.

TREATMENT 4: In case of bad test results, [name of the teacher]'s reputation as a teacher will be damaged by the publication of her class' results.

A colleague of [name of the teacher] advises her/him that to increase the probability of getting good results in the test, she/he should send her/him low-performing students to the school library to do an alternative activity during the hours of the test.

How likely do you think it is that the teacher will follow this advice?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not likely at all" and 7 indicates "Extremely likely".

- 7 Extremely likely
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 Not at all likely

If the same situation experienced by [Name of the teacher] were to happen to you in your current school, how likely would you be to follow this advice?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all likely" and 7 indicates "Extremely likely".

- 7 Extremely likely
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 Not at all likely

With an experiment inserted in the PQ we aim at exploring school leaders' strategies to improve national standardized test results. Few studies have until now focused on both formal and informal strategies adopted by school leaders to improve results when dealing with national standardized tests (Jennings, 2010). Such strategies range from those related to the use of data from assessments for instructional improvement, to changes in the curriculum and in the staff management, to cream-skimming practices to select students. With the experiment, we explore which types of pedagogical and organizational strategies are preferred by school leaders, and assess how different personal and contextual factors are related with different strategical preferences.

Two main challenges are related to the study of these strategies. Firstly, as the two strategies can coexist, it is difficult to assess the relative importance given to each of them. Secondly, as underlined above, since some of these strategies are considered as undesired effects of PBA, direct reporting on them may be affected by social desirability bias. The conjoint experimental design used in our research is a combination between 'choice-based conjoint' and 'rating-based conjoint'. Firstly, respondents are presented with two big strategies to enhance test scores and are

asked to choose the most preferred one. Each strategy involves a number of changes (features) concerning several dimensions. After choosing the preferred strategy, the respondent is asked to rate the likelihood to follow both strategies (the preferred one and the non-preferred one) in their real life.

Box 2 displays the task proposed to the respondents, the conjoint table with all the possible dimensions and features, and the two follow-up questions.

Box 2: Conjoint experiment (PQ)

Imagine that your school has obtained bad results in the last standardized test.
 You want to improve the results for the coming years. Which of the following strategies would you adopt?
 When you answer, consider that your school situation is the same as it is now: your colleagues are the same, the school inspector/s is/are the same, your students are the same, so are their parents.
 Even if you aren't entirely sure or if in your context some actions are not possible, please indicate which of the two you would prefer.

[Two potential strategies with a randomized selection of the following features are presented. The order of dimension is also randomized]

DIMENSION	[FEATURES]
Educational approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continue with current teaching practices Modify the curriculum according to the competence tested Dedicate more class time to practice for the test
Staff management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Make no change in the management of the staff Provide professional development to the teachers whose students got bad results in the test Try to place teachers whose students got bad results in grades not affected by the test
Students' targeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do not target students with any specific profile Encourage parents of high-performing students to enrol their children in your school Dissuade parents of low-performing students to enrol their children in your school
Policy for student admission in case of oversubscription	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Admit students through a lottery system Admit students based on criteria such as proximity, siblings already at the school, and having social or special needs Admit students based on their reports from previous school and/or interviews with parents

Which of the two strategies would you adopt?

- Strategy A
- Strategy B

On a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates that you would never follow Strategy A, and 7 that you would follow this strategy without a doubt, please indicate to what extent you would follow Strategy A:

- 7 I would follow Strategy A without a doubt
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 I would never follow Strategy A

On a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates that you would never follow Strategy B, and 7 that you would follow this strategy without a doubt, please indicate to what extent you would follow Strategy B:

- 7 I would follow Strategy B without a doubt
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 I would never follow Strategy B

The task is repeated twice for each respondent, each time drawing a new set of strategies from the same randomization distribution. Randomization occurs uniformly, i.e. with equal probability for all strategies to be displayed. The order of strategies was randomized as well to neutralize potential biases due to primacy effect, i.e. bias originating by the respondents mainly paying attention to the attributes that appear at the top of the conjoint table (Hainmueller et al., 2014). This conjoint experiment is not included in the Norwegian survey.

4.2 LEM and school context

4.2.1 LEM

The main aspects of LEM asked in the Survey are related to the subjective perception of competition. We indeed consider it a key variable to be taken into account when exploring the enactment of educational policies, as it may induce or inhibit certain instrumental or expressive responses (Jabbar, 2015; Van Zanten, 2009a, 2009b). Inspired by Zancajo (2017), we conceive perceived competition as made up by three main dimensions concerning: a) the number of competitors; b) the kind of competition (e.g. whether it is focalised, i.e. only a restricted number of schools are perceived as competitors or it is extensive, i.e. all schools are perceived as competitors); c) the space of competition. This last aspect refers to the geographical spaces of competition, measured as the distance covered or travelled by students, but also as the distance between the school and its competitors.

Beyond questions related to the perception of competition, we also ask questions about students' admission and selection, the level of school demand, pressure to maintain enrolment, as well as on marketing activities. Questions about collaboration with other schools try to capture the frequency, the type and the rationale of these collaborations. On this last dimension, we built the response option being inspired by the theorisation made by Peterson (1991), according to whom the motives behind collaboration can be reconducted to two types: 1) Shared Information & Mutual Support; and 2) Common Tasks & Compatible Goals. Finally, in both questionnaires we ask about school reputation. Apart from this last question, all other variables related to the LEM are collected exclusively through the PQ. Principals are those who have to find a balance between "external constraints and demands", deriving from local authorities, parents and other schools, and "internal" ones, coming, for instance, from teachers and student (Ball and Maroy, 2009). They are therefore those who more clearly perceive school positioning and participation within the LEM, as well as those who are more aware of competition dynamics between schools. Our decision to address these issues exclusively in the PQ is in line with existing literature, where perception of competition is generally analysed through questionnaires and interviews to principals (e.g., Jabbar, 2015; Musset, 2012). Table 4 shows the variables/constructs related to LEM and how we ask them in the Survey.

Table 4: LEM: variables and questions

CONSTRUCT/ VARIABLE	QUESTION WORDING	REMARKS	INSTR.						
Collaboration with other schools	<p>Does your school participate in any collaborative project, network or activity with other schools of the same level?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Yes, please indicate how many schools you collaborate with: ___ ○ No 		PQ						
Collaboration with other schools - type	<p>You said that your school collaborates with {Piped text with the number of schools the school collaborates with} schools. How many of them are:</p> <p><i>As categories are not exclusive, in each row you may indicate up to {Piped text with the number of schools the school collaborates with} schools.</i></p> <p>Neighbouring schools: ____ Schools that have a similar pedagogical approach: ____ <i>Only if not public:</i> Schools of the same religious order (if applicable): ____ <i>All cases, except Spanish ones:</i> Schools that have the same [administrator/school owner]. Other, please specify: ____</p>	[administrator/school owner] will be adapted to the cases: School board in the NL and in Norwegian private schools, “sostenedor” in Chile, municipality for Norwegian public schools).	PQ						
Collaboration with other schools - frequency	<p>How often does your school participate in collaborative projects, networks or regular activities with other schools?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Monthly or more than monthly ○ More than once a year but less than monthly ○ Once a year ○ Less than once a year 		PQ						
Collaboration with other schools - reasons	<p>Why does your school participate in these collaborative activities with other schools? <i>(Multiple answers possible)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ To share knowledge and experience ▪ To establish common ways to assess and evaluate our students ▪ To develop a common pedagogical plan ▪ To increase the visibility of our schools ▪ To influence local and/or national policy making ▪ Other, please specify: ____ 		PQ						
Factors' for students' admission	<p>How important are the following factors when students are being considered for admission to your school?</p> <p><i>Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates “Not at all important” and 7 indicates “Extremely important”.</i></p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;">Proximity of residence to the school</td> <td rowspan="5" style="width: 50%; vertical-align: middle;"> <p>For each option:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 7 Extremely important ○ 6 ○ 5 ○ 4 ○ 3 </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Proximity of the parents' workplace</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Siblings attending the school</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Parents' matching the profile of the school (including values, educational project, religious preferences, etc.)</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>All cases, except the NL:</i> The</td> </tr> </table>	Proximity of residence to the school	<p>For each option:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 7 Extremely important ○ 6 ○ 5 ○ 4 ○ 3 	Proximity of the parents' workplace	Siblings attending the school	Parents' matching the profile of the school (including values, educational project, religious preferences, etc.)	<i>All cases, except the NL:</i> The	<p>This question does not apply to Norwegian public schools. In the case of Madrid, we add the following specification to the question: “Consider also what criteria you rely on in the event of a tie between applicants”.</p>	PQ
Proximity of residence to the school	<p>For each option:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 7 Extremely important ○ 6 ○ 5 ○ 4 ○ 3 								
Proximity of the parents' workplace									
Siblings attending the school									
Parents' matching the profile of the school (including values, educational project, religious preferences, etc.)									
<i>All cases, except the NL:</i> The									

	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>school's own admission test</td> <td> ☐ 2 </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Only if school is secondary: Student achievement as indicated in their report card</td> <td> ☐ 1 Not at all important </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other, please specify:</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	school's own admission test	☐ 2	Only if school is secondary: Student achievement as indicated in their report card	☐ 1 Not at all important	Other, please specify:						
school's own admission test	☐ 2											
Only if school is secondary: Student achievement as indicated in their report card	☐ 1 Not at all important											
Other, please specify:												
Geographical provenance of the students enrolled	<p>Where do the students of this school come from? Please estimate the approximate percentage of students coming from the following areas. The total must be 100%.</p> <p>From within the school's neighbourhood: ____ From within the municipality (but beyond the school's district): ____ From other municipalities: ____</p>	<p>List of geographical areas is adapted to the different cases. This question does not apply to Norwegian public schools.</p>	PQ									
Marketing activities	<p>To promote your school, how important are the following activities?</p> <p>Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all important" and 7 indicates "Extremely important".</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Organising school open days</td> <td rowspan="8"> <p>For each option:</p> ☐ 7 Extremely important ☐ 6 ☐ 5 ☐ 4 ☐ 3 ☐ 2 ☐ 1 Not at all important </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Participating in school fairs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Primary schools of all cases, except the NL: Organising visits to Kindergarten</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Only for secondary schools: Organising visits to Kindergarten</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Updating the school website and/or the Facebook page, Instagram of the school, etc.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Giving parents the opportunity to arrange ad-hoc visits to the school</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Only for the NL: Updating information on the Vensters voor Verantwoording website</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other, please specify:</td> </tr> </table>	Organising school open days	<p>For each option:</p> ☐ 7 Extremely important ☐ 6 ☐ 5 ☐ 4 ☐ 3 ☐ 2 ☐ 1 Not at all important	Participating in school fairs	Primary schools of all cases, except the NL: Organising visits to Kindergarten	Only for secondary schools: Organising visits to Kindergarten	Updating the school website and/or the Facebook page, Instagram of the school, etc.	Giving parents the opportunity to arrange ad-hoc visits to the school	Only for the NL: Updating information on the Vensters voor Verantwoording website	Other, please specify:	<p>This question is asked only to principals and vice-principals.</p>	PQ
Organising school open days	<p>For each option:</p> ☐ 7 Extremely important ☐ 6 ☐ 5 ☐ 4 ☐ 3 ☐ 2 ☐ 1 Not at all important											
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Giving parents the opportunity to arrange ad-hoc visits to the school												
Only for the NL: Updating information on the Vensters voor Verantwoording website												
Other, please specify:												
Pressure to maintain enrolment	<p>How much pressure do you, as the {Piped text with leadership function in the school}, feel to obtain or maintain a sufficient number of students at your school?</p> <p>Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all" and 7 indicates "An extreme amount".</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ 7 An extreme amount ☐ 6 ☐ 5 ☐ 4 ☐ 3 ☐ 2 ☐ 1 Not at all 		PQ									

School demand	<p>Which best describes the number of applications compared to the available places in the school in the last three years?</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>2018/2019</td> <td rowspan="3"> <p>For each option:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Many more applications than places ☐ A few more applications than places ☐ The same number of applications as places ☐ A few more places than applications ☐ Many more places than application </td> </tr> <tr> <td>2017/2018</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2016/2017</td> </tr> </table>	2018/2019	<p>For each option:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Many more applications than places ☐ A few more applications than places ☐ The same number of applications as places ☐ A few more places than applications ☐ Many more places than application 	2017/2018	2016/2017	This question does not apply to Norwegian public schools. Years are adjusted to the year of the survey administration.	PQ
2018/2019	<p>For each option:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Many more applications than places ☐ A few more applications than places ☐ The same number of applications as places ☐ A few more places than applications ☐ Many more places than application 						
2017/2018							
2016/2017							
School reputation	<p>In comparison to other schools in the school local community, how is the reputation of your school?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Considerably above average ☐ Above average ☐ Average ☐ Below average ☐ Considerably below average 		PQ & TQ				
Subjective competition: number of competitors	<p>Approximately, how many schools would you say parents consider as an alternative to your school when deciding where to enrol their children? _____</p>	This question does not apply to Norwegian public schools.	PQ				
Subjective competition: location of competitors	<p>You said that there are {Piped text with indicated number of competitors} school/s considered by parents as an alternative to your school, where is/are this/these school/s located?</p> <p><i>The total must equal {Piped text with indicated number of competitors}.</i></p> <p>From within the school's neighbourhood: ____</p> <p>From within the municipality (but beyond the school's district: ____</p> <p>From other municipalities: ____</p>	List of geographical areas is adapted to the different cases. This question does not apply to Norwegian public schools.	PQ				
Students' selection	<table border="1"> <tr> <td> <p>...children whose parents share similar values with this school?</p> </td> <td rowspan="2"> <p>For each question:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Completely ☐ A lot ☐ Some ☐ A little ☐ Not at all </td> </tr> <tr> <td> <p>... children whose parents seem to be particularly engaged in the education of their child?</p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p>...children whose parents share similar values with this school?</p>	<p>For each question:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Completely ☐ A lot ☐ Some ☐ A little ☐ Not at all 	<p>... children whose parents seem to be particularly engaged in the education of their child?</p>	This question does not apply to Norwegian public schools.	PQ	
<p>...children whose parents share similar values with this school?</p>	<p>For each question:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Completely ☐ A lot ☐ Some ☐ A little ☐ Not at all 						
<p>... children whose parents seem to be particularly engaged in the education of their child?</p>							

4.2.2 School context

During the last decades, the crucial role of the school context in the enactment of educational policies has gained attention within the scholarly community. In this regard, literature related to the micro-politics of the school (Ball, 1987), sense-making theories (Coburn, 2005; Spillane et al., 2004), and policy enactment theory (Ball et al., 2012) have shown the relevance and the complexity of analysing the impact of context in policy re-contextualization processes. Regarding school context, the Survey collects information related to collegiality, leadership, and some key organisational and pedagogical aspects.

Following the operationalization made by Mintrop (2012), collegiality is understood, as a type of relationship between colleagues that involves sharing common goals and purposes and supporting each other. In the survey, questions aiming at measuring this type of relationship as well as collaboration between colleagues are therefore included.

Another important aspect to be taken into account regarding school context is leadership. School leaders hold a primary role in students' learning, directly or indirectly through organizational features (Leithwood et al., 2008cd). They also play a key in motivating teachers and promoting school improvement and are therefore a central piece to understand accountability policies enactment within schools (Finnigan, 2010). Following Spillane et al. (2004), we acknowledge the importance of taking into account for the fact that leadership roles are often not assumed only by the school principal. We are thus particularly interested in leadership as a distributed feature amongst educational staff. In the Survey, we explore issues such as power dispersal and participation in the decision-making (Heck and Hallinger, 2010), as well as how much influence teachers have in the decision-making. We also ask a question trying to measure whether the principal and leadership team are actively promoting and fostering the participation of teachers in the decision-making. In this sense, the concept we have in mind is similar to that of "collaborative leadership" used by Hallinger and Heck (2010). Moreover, we ask teachers whether they have any kind of formal and informal leadership and/or coordination role within the school. The TQ also contains a question asking teachers about their trust in principal as this can mediate the effect of leadership (Montecinos et al., 2014; Van Maele and Van Houtte, 2015). In the Survey, we specifically define it as the degree to which teachers believe they can rely and count on their principal/management board when they have problem or need support. Finally, we include questions on what sources of knowledge are used to gather information needed to improve teaching, on whether instruction is organised differently according to students' ability and on how and by whom teachers are evaluated.

Table 5 – School context: variables and questions

CONSTRUCT/ VARIABLE	QUESTION WORDING	REMARKS	INSTR.
Ability grouping	<p>Some schools organize instruction differently for students with different abilities.</p> <p>What is your school policy regarding this?</p> <p>Students are grouped by ability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ For all subjects ○ For some subjects ○ For some activities ○ Never 	For ability grouping, we found relevant to ask whether the groups are made according to the students' overall ability or whether different groups are made for each subject according to the student's ability in each subject. To our knowledge, this has not been done in any existing survey yet.	PQ
Ability grouping – Subjects	<p>For which subjects are students grouped by ability?</p> <p><i>(Multiple choice possible)</i></p> <p><i>[Dropdown menu with case specific subjects]</i></p>		PQ
Ability grouping – Type	<p>These groups...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ... are always the same ○ ... change according to the subject 		PQ
Collaborative leadership	<p>To what extent do teachers in this school are encouraged by the management team to give their opinions and suggestions on important school issues?</p> <p><i>Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all"</i></p>		TQ

	<p>and 7 indicates "Absolutely".</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ 7 Absolutely ☐ 6 ☐ 5 ☐ 4 ☐ 3 ☐ 2 ☐ 1 Not at all 						
Collegiality	<p>How many colleagues at this school do you feel you share your views on what the central mission of the school should be?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ With everyone ☐ With the majority of them ☐ With approximately half of them ☐ With a minority of them ☐ With no one <p>When you feel down about your teaching and/or your students, how many colleagues in this school can you count on for support?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ On everyone ☐ On the majority of them ☐ On approximately half of them ☐ On a minority of them ☐ On no one <p>To what extent is there a cooperative effort among the teaching staff in your school?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Absolutely ☐ A lot ☐ To some extent ☐ A little ☐ Not at all 		TQ				
Cooperation between teachers	<p>In this school, how often do you...</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;"> ...discuss teaching strategies and students' learning issues with colleagues? </td> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;"> For each question: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Frequently ☐ Occasionally ☐ Seldom ☐ Never </td> </tr> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;"> ...share and/or develop instructional material(s) with your colleagues? </td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	...discuss teaching strategies and students' learning issues with colleagues?	For each question: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Frequently ☐ Occasionally ☐ Seldom ☐ Never 	...share and/or develop instructional material(s) with your colleagues?			TQ
...discuss teaching strategies and students' learning issues with colleagues?	For each question: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Frequently ☐ Occasionally ☐ Seldom ☐ Never 						
...share and/or develop instructional material(s) with your colleagues?							
Leadership function in the school	<p>What is your function in this school?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Principal ☐ Vice-principal ☐ [Other relevant leadership functions according to the case] ☐ Other, please specify: 		PQ				
Leadership/coordination role - Any (informal)	<p>Do you have a leadership or coordination role such as [case-specific examples here]?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Yes ☐ No 		TQ				

<p>Leadership/coordination role/s – What (Informal)</p>	<p>Which of the following options best describes your leadership/coordination role in this school? <i>Select all that apply</i></p> <p><i>[Case-specific list of possible roles]</i> Other, please specify: _____</p>		<p>TQ</p>													
<p>School autonomy and decision-making</p>	<p>Who makes the decisions concerning this school in the following domains? <i>Please select all the actors that have some room for decision-making in the following domains.</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="459 591 1082 1263"> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 591 794 1263"> <p>Budget allocation Selection of school principals Selection of new teachers <i>All cases, except Norway: Teachers' salary increases/Teachers' promotion</i> <i>All cases, except Norway: Students' admission into the school</i> <i>All cases, except the NL: Curriculum adjustment (curricular objectives and/or content)</i> <i>For the NL: Curriculum development</i> Choice of textbooks and teaching materials Content of in-service training Assessment of teaching quality Teaching methods Students' assessment criteria and procedures <i>For the NL: Choice of eindtoets</i> <i>For the NL: Choice of LVS</i> The raising and use of private funds</p> </td> <td data-bbox="802 591 1074 1263"> <p><i>[List of case-specific relevant actors from Ministry of Education, local and regional actors to school actors].</i> I do not know</p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p>Budget allocation Selection of school principals Selection of new teachers <i>All cases, except Norway: Teachers' salary increases/Teachers' promotion</i> <i>All cases, except Norway: Students' admission into the school</i> <i>All cases, except the NL: Curriculum adjustment (curricular objectives and/or content)</i> <i>For the NL: Curriculum development</i> Choice of textbooks and teaching materials Content of in-service training Assessment of teaching quality Teaching methods Students' assessment criteria and procedures <i>For the NL: Choice of eindtoets</i> <i>For the NL: Choice of LVS</i> The raising and use of private funds</p>	<p><i>[List of case-specific relevant actors from Ministry of Education, local and regional actors to school actors].</i> I do not know</p>		<p>PQ & TQ</p>											
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<p>Sources of knowledge to improve teaching quality</p>	<p>To what extent do the following sources/practices provide useful information and guidance to improve the quality of teaching in your school?</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="459 1420 1082 2080"> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 1420 794 1476"> <p>Sharing experiences and tips with colleagues/mentors</p> </td> <td data-bbox="802 1420 1074 2080" rowspan="11"> <p>For each option:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Completely ☐ A lot ☐ Some ☐ A little ☐ Not at all X Not applicable. We do not use it. </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 1487 794 1543"> <p>Feedback from parents or guardians/students</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 1554 794 1610"> <p><i>All cases, except Chile: Feedback from inspector's service</i></p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 1621 794 1677"> <p><i>[National test] results and/or discussions around them</i></p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 1688 794 1744"> <p><i>For the NL: Student monitoring system (LVS)</i></p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 1756 794 1812"> <p>Classroom exam results.</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 1823 794 1879"> <p><i>For the NL: Classroom test results (such as Method tests)</i></p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 1890 794 1946"> <p><i>For Chile: Results of the teacher evaluation</i></p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 1957 794 2013"> <p>In-service training</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 2024 794 2080"> <p>Publications by experts (books, articles, internet, etc.)</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 2092 794 2148"> <p>External consultancy (private providers)</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 2159 794 2215"> <p><i>For Chile: Students' and parents' surveys</i></p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p>Sharing experiences and tips with colleagues/mentors</p>	<p>For each option:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Completely ☐ A lot ☐ Some ☐ A little ☐ Not at all X Not applicable. We do not use it. 	<p>Feedback from parents or guardians/students</p>	<p><i>All cases, except Chile: Feedback from inspector's service</i></p>	<p><i>[National test] results and/or discussions around them</i></p>	<p><i>For the NL: Student monitoring system (LVS)</i></p>	<p>Classroom exam results.</p>	<p><i>For the NL: Classroom test results (such as Method tests)</i></p>	<p><i>For Chile: Results of the teacher evaluation</i></p>	<p>In-service training</p>	<p>Publications by experts (books, articles, internet, etc.)</p>	<p>External consultancy (private providers)</p>	<p><i>For Chile: Students' and parents' surveys</i></p>		<p>PQ & TQ</p>
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	<p><i>For Chile:</i> Feedback from the Supervisor of the Ministry of Education</p> <p><i>For Chile:</i> Feedback from the Quality Agency</p> <p><i>For Chile:</i> Results of SEPA tests</p> <p><i>For Chile:</i> Feedback from the “Sostenedor”</p> <p><i>For Norway:</i> “Medarbejderundersøkelse”</p> <p><i>For the NL:</i> Feedback from the school board</p> <p>Other, please specify: _____</p>			
Teachers’ evaluation - actors	<p>In this school, who evaluates your work? <i>Please mark as many options as appropriate.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ For the Spanish cases: The school inspectorate ▪ For Chile: The Quality Agency and/or the “Superintendence” ▪ The principal and/or the leadership team ▪ For Norway: The immediate leader ▪ Other teachers ▪ Yourself (self-evaluation) ▪ For Chile: External consultant/s (private provider/s) ▪ Other, please specify: _____ 			TQ
Teachers’ evaluation - inspector’s tools	<p>Which tools/sources of information are used by the inspector to evaluate your work? <i>Please mark as many choices as appropriate.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...) ▪ Student results in the [national tests] ▪ Classroom observation ▪ Student and parent surveys ▪ Students’ work and results in the classroom ▪ Other, please specify: _____ 	This question only applies to the Spanish cases.		TQ
Teachers’ evaluation - Agency of Quality and/or “Superintendence”’s tools	<p>Which tools/sources of information are used by the Agency of Quality and/or the “Superintendence” to evaluate your work? <i>Please mark as many choices as appropriate.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...) ▪ Student results in the [national tests] ▪ Classroom observation ▪ Results of the teachers’ evaluation ▪ Student and parent surveys ▪ Students’ work and results in the classroom ▪ Other, please specify: _____ 	This question only applies to Chile.		TQ
Teachers’ evaluation - principal’s tools	<p>Which tools/sources of information are used by the principal and/or leadership team to evaluate your work? <i>Please mark as many choices as appropriate.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...) ▪ Student results in the [national tests] ▪ Classroom observation ▪ <i>For Chile:</i> Results of the teachers’ evaluation ▪ <i>For Norway:</i> Annual development meetings ▪ <i>For Chile:</i> Results of other external tests (e.g. SEPA test) ▪ <i>For Norwegian secondary schools:</i> Analysis of your students’ final exams’ results 	In the NL, we ask about eindtoets and LVS separately here.		TQ

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Student and parent surveys ▪ Students' work and results in the classroom ▪ Other, please specify: _____ 		
Teachers' evaluation - immediate leader's tools	<p>Which tools/sources of information are used by the immediate leader to evaluate your work? <i>Please mark as many choices as appropriate.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...) ▪ Student results in the [national tests] ▪ Classroom observation ▪ Student and parent surveys ▪ Students' work and results in the classroom ▪ Annual development meetings ▪ Analysis of your students' final exams' results ▪ Other, please specify: _____ 	This question only applies to Norway.	TQ
Teachers' evaluation -other teachers' tools	<p>Which tools/sources of information are used by other teachers to evaluate your work? <i>Please mark as many choices as appropriate.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...) ▪ Classroom observation ▪ Other, please specify: _____ 	This question only applies to Chile.	TQ
Teachers' evaluation -own tools	<p>Which tools/sources of information do you use to evaluate your work? <i>Please mark as many choices as appropriate.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...) ▪ Student results in the [national tests] ▪ <i>For Chile:</i> Results of other external tests (e.g. SEPA test) ▪ <i>For Norwegian secondary schools:</i> Analysis of your students' final exams' results ▪ Student and parent surveys ▪ Students' work and results in the classroom ▪ Other, please specify: _____ 	In the NL, we ask about eindtoets and LVS separately here.	TQ
Teachers' evaluation - external consultants' tools	<p>Which tools/sources of information are used by the external consultant to evaluate your work? <i>Please mark as many choices as appropriate.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...) ▪ Student results in the [national tests] ▪ Classroom observation ▪ Results of the teachers' evaluation ▪ <i>For Chile:</i> Results of other external tests (e.g. SEPA test) ▪ Student and parent surveys ▪ Students' work and results in the classroom ▪ Other, please specify: _____ 	This question only applies to Chile.	TQ
Teachers' trust in principal	<p>To what extent do teachers in this school feel they can consult the principal/management team when they have a problem?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Absolutely ○ A lot ○ To some extent ○ A little ○ Not at all 		TQ

	<p>To what extent does the principal/management team support teachers when they need it?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Absolutely ☐ A lot ☐ To some extent ☐ A little ☐ Not at all 		
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4.3 Commercial Education Improvement Services (CEIS)

Accountability systems put pressure on schools to improve their results, usually in the short/middle term. This has contributed to the proliferation of a broad range of school improvement services and materials usually provided by the private sector. We name them commercial educational improvement services (CEIS). CEIS include materials and services related to lessons’ plan and instructional support, curriculum design, test preparation, behavioural management, teacher training and personal development, as well as edu-marketing and students’ recruitment services. CEIS also embrace ICT (such as tablets and related learning platforms) and consultancy services for schools (Burch, 2009, Verger et al. 2017).

With the emergence of PBA, a whole industry sector focusing on testing and measurement has specially developed. A number of companies specialize in the evaluation and tracking of children’s learning outcomes and, on the basis of these data, sell education improvement services to countries, local governments, schools and/or families (Hogan et al., 2015, 2016).

In the Survey we are interested in exploring to what extent CEIS are penetrating at the school level and which sectors of this industry are more expanded than others. In the Survey, we ask whether principals about the use of CEIS within the school, who the purchasers are, and if relevant, the percentage of school budget devoted to the acquisition of such services, as well as principals’ opinion on their value for money.

Table 6 – CEIS: variables and questions

CONSTRUCT/ VARIABLE	QUESTION WORDING	INSTR.		
CEIS - Budget	<p>Approximately, what percentage of the school’s budget goes to the acquisition of educational services and products delivered to the school by private companies (including publishers)? <i>[Slider from 0 to 100]</i></p>	PQ		
CEIS - Purchasers	<p>Who have been the main agents acquiring these resources for the school? (Multiple choice possible)</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;"> <p>[List of previously selected services]</p> </td> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;"> <p><u>For each service:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ [Case-specific list of actors] ▪ The school ▪ Personally (bought with my own money) ▪ Other </td> </tr> </table>	<p>[List of previously selected services]</p>	<p><u>For each service:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ [Case-specific list of actors] ▪ The school ▪ Personally (bought with my own money) ▪ Other 	PQ
<p>[List of previously selected services]</p>	<p><u>For each service:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ [Case-specific list of actors] ▪ The school ▪ Personally (bought with my own money) ▪ Other 			

CEIS - Use	<p>In the last 12 months, how often have you used any of these educational resources delivered by private companies (including publishers)?</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="467 315 1297 622"> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 315 882 349">Lesson plans (online or paper)</td> <td data-bbox="882 315 1297 622" rowspan="4"> <p>For each item:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ More than once a month ☐ Once a month ☐ More than once but less than monthly ☐ Once ☐ Never </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 349 882 383">Test preparation resources</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 383 882 439">Consultancy/training services on instructional improvement</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="467 439 882 622">All cases, except Norwegian public schools: Edu-marketing/students' recruitment's services</td> </tr> </table>	Lesson plans (online or paper)	<p>For each item:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ More than once a month ☐ Once a month ☐ More than once but less than monthly ☐ Once ☐ Never 	Test preparation resources	Consultancy/training services on instructional improvement	All cases, except Norwegian public schools: Edu-marketing/students' recruitment's services	PQ
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Test preparation resources							
Consultancy/training services on instructional improvement							
All cases, except Norwegian public schools: Edu-marketing/students' recruitment's services							
CEIS- Value for money	<p>How do you rate the value for money of the resources that private companies (including publishers) deliver?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Very good ☐ Good ☐ Bad ☐ Very bad 	PQ					

4.4 Respondents' personal and professional information

The Survey also includes a number of questions asking about personal and professional information. A part from basic demographic information, we ask, more specifically, about issues related with respondents' job within schools, the subjects and grades taught, the contract status, other professional experience and workload in the school. We also ask about the percentage of time spent in different work tasks and what would be their ideal dedication to these tasks if they could choose.

The questionnaires also collect information about the degrees owned and the year of obtainment of teacher education, as well as political ideology, union membership and associationism. In the Chilean questionnaires, one question measures public service motivation. This has been initially defined as "an individual predisposition to respond to motives grounded primarily or uniquely in public institutions" (Perry and Wise, 1990: 368) with a stark focus on public service workers. Its definition has shifted more recently towards a bigger emphasis on a broader ethical dimension coming to signify "an individual's orientation to delivering service to people with the purpose of doing good for others and society" (Hondeghem and Perry 2009: 6).

Finally, two last variables try to measure job satisfaction and teacher self-efficacy. "Job satisfaction" can be defined as the gratification that individual get from their employment. We consider it a policy-relevant variable because it may be related to different issues, such as a mismatch between preferences and practices, the relationship with colleagues and with the school leaders, and so on. Different ways to measure job satisfaction exist. One item-measures asking directly for an answer have demonstrated to not be so reliable and to potentially lead to overestimating satisfaction (Saris and Gallhofer, 2014). In the questionnaires, we measure it through a combination of the direct item "All in all, I am satisfied with my job" and with other items aiming at measuring the two main dimensions that made up the construct: "satisfaction with the current school" and "satisfaction with the teaching profession". In this regard, the question contained in TALIS 2013 teachers' questionnaire appears to be well suited to our purposes. Teacher self-efficacy is the "teacher's belief or conviction that he or she can influence how well students learn, even those who may be difficult or unmotivated" (Guskey, 1987: 41). It is made up of two main dimensions: 1) Personal teaching efficacy; and 2) General teaching efficacy. The question we use in our questionnaire is an adaptation of the one proposed by Hoy and Woolfolk (1993).

Table 7 – Personal and professional information collected

CONSTRUCT/ VARIABLE	QUESTION WORDING	REMARKS	INSTR.
Age	Please indicate your age (in digits): -----		PQ & TQ
Contract status	<i>All cases, except Spanish ones: Is your current contract in this school a...</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Permanent contract ○ <i>Only for Norway and the NL: Fixed term contract, more than years</i> ○ Fixed term contract, 1-3 years ○ Fixed term contract, less than 1 year ○ <i>For Chile: "Contracto por honorarios"</i> <i>For Spanish cases: In this school are you...</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Civil servant ○ "Interino" ○ "Substituto" ○ Other, please specify: _____ 		PQ & TQ
Contract type	Is your employment in this school: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Full time ○ Part time 	This question does not apply to Norwegian public schools and to principals of all cases.	PQ & TQ
Currently teaching	Are you currently teaching? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Yes ○ No 		PQ
Current working in other schools	Are you currently working in any other school? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ No ○ Yes, in a public school ○ Yes, in a private school ○ Yes, in an independent publicly funded school 		PQ & TQ
Degrees owned	Which of the following degrees/certificates do you hold? <i>(Multiple choice possible)</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>[Case-specific list of degrees]</i> ▪ Other, please specify:... 		PQ & TQ
Gender	Please indicate your gender <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Male ○ Female ○ Other 		PQ & TQ
Grade taught	Which grade(s) are you teaching this school year? <i>[Case-specific list of grades]</i>		PQ & TQ

<p>Job satisfaction</p>	<p>To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="443 282 1106 813"> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 282 743 349">I would like to move to another school if it were possible</td> <td data-bbox="751 282 1106 813" rowspan="7"> <p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly agree ☐ Agree ☐ Neither agree nor disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Strongly disagree </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 349 743 383">I enjoy working at this school</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 383 743 439">I would recommend my school as a good place to work</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 439 743 562">If I could decide again, I would still choose to work as a {Piped text with function in the school}</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 562 743 663">I wonder whether it would have been better to choose another profession</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 663 743 752">I regret that I decided to become a {Piped text with function in the school}</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 752 743 813">All in all, I am satisfied with my job</td> </tr> </table>	I would like to move to another school if it were possible	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly agree ☐ Agree ☐ Neither agree nor disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Strongly disagree 	I enjoy working at this school	I would recommend my school as a good place to work	If I could decide again, I would still choose to work as a {Piped text with function in the school}	I wonder whether it would have been better to choose another profession	I regret that I decided to become a {Piped text with function in the school}	All in all, I am satisfied with my job		<p>PQ & TQ</p>
I would like to move to another school if it were possible	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly agree ☐ Agree ☐ Neither agree nor disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Strongly disagree 										
I enjoy working at this school											
I would recommend my school as a good place to work											
If I could decide again, I would still choose to work as a {Piped text with function in the school}											
I wonder whether it would have been better to choose another profession											
I regret that I decided to become a {Piped text with function in the school}											
All in all, I am satisfied with my job											
<p>Political ideology</p>	<p>To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="443 896 1106 1216"> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 896 743 985">The government should take measures to reduce differences in income levels</td> <td data-bbox="751 896 1106 1216" rowspan="3"> <p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly Agree ☐ Agree ☐ Neither Agree nor Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Strongly Disagree </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 985 743 1075">Workers need strong trade unions to protect their working conditions and wages</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 1075 743 1216">The less the government intervenes in the economy, the better it is for the country</td> </tr> </table>	The government should take measures to reduce differences in income levels	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly Agree ☐ Agree ☐ Neither Agree nor Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Strongly Disagree 	Workers need strong trade unions to protect their working conditions and wages	The less the government intervenes in the economy, the better it is for the country	<p>This question comes from the European Social Survey.</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>				
The government should take measures to reduce differences in income levels	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly Agree ☐ Agree ☐ Neither Agree nor Disagree ☐ Disagree ☐ Strongly Disagree 										
Workers need strong trade unions to protect their working conditions and wages											
The less the government intervenes in the economy, the better it is for the country											
<p>Previous experience as a principal/other member of leadership team in any other school</p>	<p>In the past have you ever been the principal or part of the management team in any other school?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Yes ☐ No 		<p>PQ & TQ</p>								
<p>Previous experience as a teacher in this school</p>	<p>Before your recruitment as {Piped text with leadership function in the school}, were you a teacher in this school?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Yes ☐ No 		<p>PQ</p>								
<p>Professional association membership</p>	<p>Are you a member of a professional association (collegial or pedagogical) or do you take part in a campaign or platform in the field of education?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Yes ☐ No 	<p>This question does not apply to Norway.</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>								
<p>Professional association membership - Name of association/s</p>	<p>Please indicate the name of the association/s or platforms/campaigns you are a member of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>[Case-specific list of associations]</i> ▪ Other, please specify: _____ 	<p>This question does not apply to Norway.</p>	<p>PQ & TQ</p>								

Public service motivation	<p>To what extent do the following statements apply to you?</p> <p>Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all" and 7 indicates "Completely".</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="443 376 1106 685"> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 376 762 439">I think equal opportunities for citizens are very important</td> <td data-bbox="770 376 1106 439" rowspan="4"> <p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ 7 Completely ☐ 6 ☐ 5 ☐ 4 ☐ 3 ☐ 2 ☐ 1 Not at all </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 439 762 501">It is important for me to contribute to the common good</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 501 762 564">I empathise with people who face difficulties</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 564 762 685">I would agree to a good plan to make life better for the poor, even if it costs me money</td> </tr> </table>	I think equal opportunities for citizens are very important	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ 7 Completely ☐ 6 ☐ 5 ☐ 4 ☐ 3 ☐ 2 ☐ 1 Not at all 	It is important for me to contribute to the common good	I empathise with people who face difficulties	I would agree to a good plan to make life better for the poor, even if it costs me money	This question applies only to the Chilean case.	PQ & TQ	
I think equal opportunities for citizens are very important	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ 7 Completely ☐ 6 ☐ 5 ☐ 4 ☐ 3 ☐ 2 ☐ 1 Not at all 								
It is important for me to contribute to the common good									
I empathise with people who face difficulties									
I would agree to a good plan to make life better for the poor, even if it costs me money									
Salary	<p>¿Cuál es tu remuneración salarial bruto (y sin bonificaciones)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Sobre \$2.000.000 ☐ De \$1.701.000 a \$2.000.000 ☐ De \$1.301.000 a \$1.700.000 ☐ De \$900.000 a \$1.300.000 ☐ Menor a \$900.000 	This is a Chilean case specific question. This is why it is available only in Spanish.	PQ & TQ						
Subject taught	<p>Which subject(s) are you teaching this school year?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ [Case-specific list of subjects] ☐ Other, please specify:___ 		PQ & TQ						
Teacher education	<p>Which of the following degree(s) has/have given you the right to teach? [List of previously selected degree]</p>		PQ & TQ						
Teacher education - Year of obtainment	<p>What year did you complete this/these degree/s? [Dropdown menu with years]</p>		PQ & TQ						
Teacher self-efficacy	<p>To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="443 1357 1106 2085"> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 1357 738 1514">If a student did not remember information I gave in a previous lesson, I would know how to increase his/her retention in the next lesson</td> <td data-bbox="746 1357 1106 2085" rowspan="5"> <p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly Agree ☐ Moderately Agree ☐ Agree slightly more than Disagree ☐ Disagree slightly more than Agree ☐ Moderately Disagree ☐ Strongly Disagree </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 1514 738 1671">If a student in my class becomes disruptive and noisy, I feel assured that I know some techniques to redirect him/her quickly</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 1671 738 1760">If students aren't disciplined at home, they aren't likely to accept any discipline at school</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 1760 738 1939">A teacher is very limited in what he/she can achieve because a student's home environment has a large influence on his/her achievement</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="443 1939 738 2085">When it comes right down to it, a teacher really can't do much because most of a student's motivation and performance depends on his or</td> </tr> </table>	If a student did not remember information I gave in a previous lesson, I would know how to increase his/her retention in the next lesson	<p>For each statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Strongly Agree ☐ Moderately Agree ☐ Agree slightly more than Disagree ☐ Disagree slightly more than Agree ☐ Moderately Disagree ☐ Strongly Disagree 	If a student in my class becomes disruptive and noisy, I feel assured that I know some techniques to redirect him/her quickly	If students aren't disciplined at home, they aren't likely to accept any discipline at school	A teacher is very limited in what he/she can achieve because a student's home environment has a large influence on his/her achievement	When it comes right down to it, a teacher really can't do much because most of a student's motivation and performance depends on his or		TQ
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	<p>her home environment</p> <p>If I really try hard, I can get through to even the most difficult or unmotivated students</p>							
Teacher union membership	<p>Are you a member of a teacher union?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Yes ☐ No ☐ For Norway: I prefer not to answer 		PQ & TQ					
Teacher union membership - Name of teacher union	<p>Which union are you a member of?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ [Case-specific list of associations] ☐ Other, please specify: _____ 		PQ & TQ					
Year of start of current leadership function in the present school	<p>In what year did you become the {Piped text with leadership function in the school} of this school?</p> <p>[Dropdown menu with years]</p>		PQ					
Year of start working in the present school	<p>For PQ: What year did you start working in this school?</p> <p>[Dropdown menu with years]</p> <p>For TQ: What year did start working as a teacher in this school?</p> <p>[Dropdown menu with years]</p>		PQ & TQ					
Year of start working within schools in general	<p>What year did you start working in the education sector?</p> <p>[Dropdown menu with years]</p>		PQ & TQ					
Working load - Extra-hours worked	<p>How often during the year do you work more than your contracted weekly hours?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ All or almost all weeks ☐ Frequently (many weeks per year) ☐ Occasionally (some weeks a year) ☐ Seldom (very few weeks a year) ☐ Never 		PQ & TQ					
Working load - N. of working hours	<p>How many hours a week are you employed in this school?</p> <p>[Dropdown menu with n. of hours]</p>	This question does not apply to Norway.	PQ & TQ					
Working load - % worked in the present school	<p>What percentage are you employed in this school?</p> <p>----%</p>	This question only applies to Norway.	TQ					
Working tasks – for principals and members of leadership team	<p>In a normal school week, what percentage of your working hours do you approximately spend on each of the following tasks in your role as {Piped text with leadership function in the school} in this school?</p> <p>Sum must be 100%.</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;">Administrative management (budget, human resources management, etc.)</td> <td rowspan="4" style="width: 50%; vertical-align: middle;"> <p>For each task:</p> <p>[Slider from 0 to 100]</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Pedagogical management (curriculum, pedagogical planning, etc.)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Producing reports and the school plan, filling-in forms, uploading information into online platforms, etc.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Interactions with parents/guardians</td> </tr> </table>	Administrative management (budget, human resources management, etc.)	<p>For each task:</p> <p>[Slider from 0 to 100]</p>	Pedagogical management (curriculum, pedagogical planning, etc.)	Producing reports and the school plan, filling-in forms, uploading information into online platforms, etc.	Interactions with parents/guardians		PQ
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Interactions with parents/guardians								

	<p>Analysis of test results and discussion of students' and school's performance</p> <p>Other, please specify: ____</p>										
Working tasks – for principals and members of leadership team / Preferences	<p>Ideally, in a normal school week, what percentage of your working hours should you be able to spend on these tasks to carry out your professional responsibilities in the best possible way? Sum must 100%.</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Administrative management (budget, human resources management, etc.)</td> <td rowspan="6"> <p>For each task:</p> <p>[Slider from 0 to 100]</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Pedagogical management (curriculum, pedagogical planning, etc.)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Producing reports and the school plan, filling-in forms, uploading information into online platforms, etc.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Interactions with parents/guardians</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Analysis of test results and discussion of students' and school's performance</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other, please specify: ____</td> </tr> </table>	Administrative management (budget, human resources management, etc.)	<p>For each task:</p> <p>[Slider from 0 to 100]</p>	Pedagogical management (curriculum, pedagogical planning, etc.)	Producing reports and the school plan, filling-in forms, uploading information into online platforms, etc.	Interactions with parents/guardians	Analysis of test results and discussion of students' and school's performance	Other, please specify: ____		PQ	
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Other, please specify: ____											
Working tasks – for teachers	<p>In a normal school week, what percentage of your working hours do you approximately spend on each of the following tasks? Sum must be 100%.</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Teaching in the classroom</td> <td rowspan="7"> <p>For each task:</p> <p>[Slider from 0 to 100]</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Producing reports, filling in forms, uploading information onto online platforms, as requested by the management</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Preparing lessons, marking students' work</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Discussing and sharing professional ideas and tips with colleagues</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Interactions with parents/guardians</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Professional learning/development activities</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other, please specify: ____</td> </tr> </table>	Teaching in the classroom	<p>For each task:</p> <p>[Slider from 0 to 100]</p>	Producing reports, filling in forms, uploading information onto online platforms, as requested by the management	Preparing lessons, marking students' work	Discussing and sharing professional ideas and tips with colleagues	Interactions with parents/guardians	Professional learning/development activities	Other, please specify: ____		TQ
Teaching in the classroom	<p>For each task:</p> <p>[Slider from 0 to 100]</p>										
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Working tasks – for teachers / Preferences	<p>Ideally, in a normal school week, what percentage of your working hours should you be able to spend on these tasks to carry out your professional responsibilities in the best possible way? Sum must 100%.</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Teaching in the classroom</td> <td rowspan="7"> <p>For each task:</p> <p>[Slider from 0 to 100]</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Producing reports, filling in forms, uploading information onto online platforms, as requested by the management</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Preparing lessons, marking students' work</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Discussing and sharing professional ideas and tips with colleagues</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Interactions with parents/guardians</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Professional learning/development activities</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other, please specify: ____</td> </tr> </table>	Teaching in the classroom	<p>For each task:</p> <p>[Slider from 0 to 100]</p>	Producing reports, filling in forms, uploading information onto online platforms, as requested by the management	Preparing lessons, marking students' work	Discussing and sharing professional ideas and tips with colleagues	Interactions with parents/guardians	Professional learning/development activities	Other, please specify: ____		TQ
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Discussing and sharing professional ideas and tips with colleagues											
Interactions with parents/guardians											
Professional learning/development activities											
Other, please specify: ____											

4.5 Investigating teachers' motivation: a survey experiment

In PBA systems school actors face consequences of a different nature (individual, collective, reputation or material) according to their levels of performance and adhesion to centrally-defined learning standards. Salary bonuses and other financial rewards constitute one type of material consequences at stake in PBA systems that have been introduced in some contexts to reward teachers and schools whose students have performed better – or have shown better progression – in the national standardized test. The idea behind is that the perspective of gaining a bonus stimulate teachers' motivation and, consequently, foster the quality of their teaching and their effort to prepare them adequately for the test.

Behavioural sciences literature considers external rewards as ways to booster extrinsic motivation (Ryan and Deci, 2000). Literature has however longer argued that teachers are principally intrinsically motivated (Lortie, 1975; Johnson, 1986; Firestone and Pennell, 1993; Mintrop and Ordenes, 2017), i.e. their engagement is motivated by personal desire, the enjoyability of the experience, the identification with the profession, etc., independently from external factors. Considering this, it remains unclear whether these kinds of material incentives really have the potential of fostering teachers' motivation and under what circumstances.

Directly asking teachers about their work motives may be challenging. Indeed, motives such as social commitment, defined as the desire to do efforts for the benefit of others (Grant, 2008), have longer shaped the idealistic imaginary of the good teacher (Lortie, 1975). There are thus reasons to hypothesize that because of social desirability, teachers will be not so prone to admit they are motivated by extrinsic rewards, or more specifically, by a financial incentive if explicitly asked.

To explore teachers' motivation and, more specifically, the motivational strength of salary bonuses, we designed a conjoint-survey experiment and included it in the TQ. In the experiment, responding teachers are asked to choose between different working scenarios that simultaneously varied in five of their characteristics. This design allows us to compare on a common scale the strength of each characteristic in explaining the preference for a given working scenario and studying teachers' preferences over multiple dimensions. As displayed in Box 3, the conjoint design used is the same as the experiment included in the PQ. It is about a mixture between 'choice-based conjoint' and 'rating-based conjoint': respondents are asked to choose the most preferred working scenario and, after choosing it, they are asked to rate the likelihood to prefer each scenario (both the chosen one and the other one) in a real life situation.

As in the conjoint experiment inserted in the PQ, the task is repeated twice for each respondent. Randomization occurred uniformly and the order of the different dimensions was randomized to neutralise potential order effect biases (Hainmueller et al., 2014).

Box 3: Conjoint experiment (TQ)

Below we present you with two pairs of school that differ in some aspects.
Please indicate which school you would prefer to work in, if you could choose one of them.
The scenarios are hypothetical and may not correspond to the real conditions existing in your context.
Even if you aren't entirely sure, please indicate which of the two schools you would prefer.

[Two potential schools with a randomized selection of the following features are presented. The order of dimension is also randomized]

DIMENSION	[FEATURES]
Pro-social commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advantaged (easy-to-teach students) • Mixed ability (diversity of learning paces) • Struggling (hard-to-teach students)
Type of assessment of teaching quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessed on the basis of students' national test results • Assessed on the basis of classroom observation

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Assessed on the basis of teacher’s portfolio
Goal-setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goals are well defined and well communicated • Goals are not always clear and well communicated • No performance goals are set
Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The principal is engaged and very supportive • Parents are engaged and very supportive” • The other teachers are engaged and very supportive
External material rewards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yearly salary bonus for individual teachers according to teaching assessment results • Yearly budgetary rewards for the school according to teaching assessments results at the school level • No salary bonuses or budgetary rewards attached to the teaching assessment

Which of the two schools would you prefer?

- School A
- School B

On a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates that you would never work in School A, and 7 that you would work there without a doubt, please indicate to what extent you would work in School A if you could choose:

- 7 I would work in School A without a doubt
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 I would never choose to work in School A

On a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates that you would never work in School B, and 7 that you would work there without a doubt, please indicate to what extent you would work in School B if you could choose:

- 7 I would work in School B without a doubt
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 I would never choose to work in School B

5. Conclusion and remaining challenges

“Survey experiences are rarely documented, and when they are, they are often not sufficiently self-critical” (Beauchemin, 2012: 36). This often hinders other researchers’ understanding of how data have been collected and of data flaws. The REFORMED Survey delivers unique and rich datasets, but it is important to highlight its limits not only to call users to pay attention to them, but also to make it possible to overcome them in future research.

The REFORMED Survey delivers large-scale datasets that can be used to explore and analyse the enactment of accountability policies in different contexts, by taking into account information regarding the local education market where the sampled schools are located as well as school-level and individual level relevant variables. As explained in this note, the conception and development of the REFORMED questionnaires have involved a number of steps aiming at attaining a good level of data comparability across cases and at obtaining high-quality data. Nevertheless, as in every Survey, some aspects should be regarded with caution.

A first aspect that should be regarded with attention is connected to the length of the REFORMED questionnaires. Collecting comprehensive information on different relevant aspects has the price to make the questionnaires long. The pilots carried out revealed that the completion time for the PQ ranges from 18 to 35 minutes, whereas this was from 25 to even 50 minutes for the TQ. This length may bring to satisficing responses (Krosnick, 1991; Revilla and Ochoa, 2013), i.e. respondents answering without the required cognitive effort, and to higher dropout rates, especially in the cases where the Survey has been administrated online. Information on the modes of Survey implementation, data coverage, response and completion rates, as well as on data quality checks will be the object of future methodological notes.

A second aspect that is worthy of attention is related to the cross-sectional nature of the REFORMED Survey, which constitutes one of its main limitations. Indeed, it does not allow to establish changes over time, nor to evaluate the impact of the introduction of SAWA policies on what school actors think and do.

The exploration of SAWA policies interpretation is not exempt from difficulties. Interpretation is a highly interactive and recursive process (Coburn, 2001), so that the Survey, as the majority of existing studies, captures attitudes in one moment in time, thus neglecting the dynamic nature of the process. A further difficulty is related to the originality of this module of the Survey. To the best of our knowledge, the REFORMED Project is pioneer in trying to capture, in-depth, attitudes towards SAWA policies in a quantitative manner. This module thus constitutes a genuine contribution of the Project, but comes with the typical uncertainties of innovative research endeavours.

The investigation of SAWA policies’ translation into practice is also challenging from an analytical point of view. Indeed, it is very difficult to identify causal relationships between the perceived pressure coming from PBA and school practices. On the one hand, even if it is true that some practices can be reconducted to the existence of PBA policies (curriculum narrowing or alignment, teaching to the test, use of test’s data, cheating practices), this does not mean that these practices are a direct effect of the pressure generated by the PBA system, as other mechanisms can be at stake. On the other hand, practices that may exist independently from the existence of PBA (pedagogical approaches, practices regarding teacher evaluation, ability grouping), could actually be a response to the testing system, but it is difficult to identify, in an unequivocal way, whether these practices would be at place if a PBA system was not present, or even if the PBA involved different stakes.

In the framework of the REFORMED Project, we try to overcome such weaknesses by complementing and triangulating data coming from the Survey with qualitative information coming from in-depth interviews. Still, the data coming from the Survey are valuable also by themselves. The Survey delivers data that can definitively contribute to existing knowledge on SAWA policies’ enactment in many ways. It enables to investigate whether specific attitudes towards PBA and autonomy, as well as some practices, are more likely to be present in specific contexts through the comparison between different settings. The Survey also allows to link school actors’ interpretation of SAWA policies, as well the pressure PBA generates, with specific practices. Differences and

similarities between different generations of teachers and principals (who have experienced different policy contexts) could be also studied. The analysis of the experiments included in the Survey furthermore allows exploring sensitive topics in an innovative way.

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APPENDIX: REFORMED SOURCE QUESTIONNAIRES⁹

Principal questionnaire

The REFORMED team cordially invites you to participate in this survey focusing on schools' organizational dynamics, educational practices, and teaching methods, as well as teachers' and school leaders' opinions on and experiences with recent educational reforms.

Your participation will make an invaluable contribution to our research!

The survey will take around **30 minutes** to complete.

The data collected from the survey will be anonymized and securely stored. This study follows the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The survey is completely voluntary and you may opt out at any time. By completing and submitting the survey, you give informed consent to participate in the study.

Many thanks for your collaboration!

If you have any questions about this project, do not hesitate to contact us at [e-mail address of case responsible]

---Page Break---

WHAT IS YOUR FUNCTION IN THIS SCHOOL?

- Principal
- Vice-principal
- [Other relevant leadership functions according to the case]
- Other, please specify: _____

---Page Break---

WHAT YEAR DID YOU START WORKING IN THIS SCHOOL?

[Dropdown menu with years]

BEFORE YOUR RECRUITMENT AS [PIPED TEXT WITH LEADERSHIP FUNCTION] WERE YOU A TEACHER IN THIS SCHOOL?

- Yes
- No

---Page Break---

Display if have been previously a teacher of the school = Yes

IN WHAT YEAR DID YOU BECOME THE [PIPED TEXT WITH LEADERSHIP FUNCTION] OF THIS SCHOOL?

[Dropdown menu with years]

IN THE PAST HAVE YOU EVER BEEN THE PRINCIPAL OR PART OF THE MANAGEMENT TEAM IN ANY OTHER SCHOOL?

- Yes
- No

---Page Break---

⁹ Source questionnaires do not include country-specific questions when these apply only to one country case. For these questions, see the methodological note or the country-specific questionnaires.

PLEASE INDICATE YOUR GENDER:

- Male
- Female
- Other

PLEASE INDICATE YOUR AGE (IN DIGITS):

---Page Break---

WE WILL START BY ASKING YOU SOME QUESTIONS ABOUT YOUR SCHOOL.

All cases, except Norway public schools

WHERE DO THE STUDENTS OF THIS SCHOOL TRAVEL FROM?

Please estimate the approximate percentage of students travelling from the following areas.
 The total must be 100%.

From within the school's neighbourhood: ____

From within the municipality (but beyond the school's district: ____

From other municipalities: ____

[Other case-specific options]

---Page Break---

All cases, except Norway public schools

OVER THE LAST THREE YEARS, TO WHAT EXTENT HAVE YOU TRIED TO ENROLL...

	Not at all	A little	Some	A lot	Completely
...children whose parents share similar values with this school?	☐				
... children whose parents seem to be particularly engaged in the education of their child?	☐				

---Page Break---

All cases, except Norway public schools

HOW IMPORTANT ARE THE FOLLOWING FACTORS WHEN STUDENTS ARE BEING CONSIDERED FOR ADMISSION TO YOUR SCHOOL?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates “Not at all important” and 7 indicates “Extremely important”.

	Not at all important 1	2	3	4	5	6	Extremely important 7
Proximity of residence to the school	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Proximity of the parents' workplace	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Siblings attending the school	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Parents' matching the profile of the school (including values, educational project, religious preferences, etc.)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
<i>case is not The Netherlands</i>							
The school's own admission test	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
<i>Only for secondary schools</i>							
Student achievement as indicated in their report card	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Other, please specify:	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

All cases, except Norway public schools

WHICH BEST DESCRIBES THE NUMBER OF APPLICATIONS COMPARED TO THE AVAILABLE PLACES IN THE SCHOOL IN THE LAST THREE YEARS?

	Many more places than applications	A few more places than applications	The same number of applications as places	A few applications more than places	Many applications more than places
2018/2019	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
2017/2018	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
2016/2017	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

Display This Question if Leadership function in the school = principal or vice-principal

TO PROMOTE YOUR SCHOOL, HOW IMPORTANT ARE THE FOLLOWING ACTIVITIES?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates “Not at all important” and 7 indicates “Extremely important”.

	Not important at 1	2	3	4	5	6	Extremely important 7
Organizing school open days	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Participating in school fairs	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
<i>For primary schools and not The Netherlands</i>							
Organizing visits to Kindergarten	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
<i>For secondary schools</i>							
Organizing visits to primary schools	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Updating the school website and/or the Facebook page, Instagram of the school, etc.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Giving parents the opportunity to arrange ad-hoc visits to the school	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
<i>The Netherlands</i>							
Updating information on the Vensters voor Verantwoording website	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Other, please specify:	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

All cases except Norway (public schools)

APPROXIMATELY, HOW MANY SCHOOLS WOULD YOU SAY PARENTS CONSIDER AS AN ALTERNATIVE TO YOUR SCHOOL WHEN DECIDING WHERE TO ENROLL THEIR CHILDREN? _____

---Page Break---

Display This Question if case is not Norway (public schools) And If Number of competitors is Greater Than 0

YOU SAID THAT THERE ARE [N. OF COMPETITORS] SCHOOL/S CONSIDERED BY PARENTS AS AN ALTERNATIVE TO YOUR SCHOOL, WHERE IS/ARE THIS/THESE SCHOOL/S LOCATED?

The total must equal [n. of competitors]

From within the school's neighbourhood: _____

From within the municipality (but beyond the school's district: _____

From other municipalities: _____

[Other case-specific options]

---Page Break---

IN COMPARISON TO OTHER SCHOOLS IN THE SCHOOL LOCAL COMMUNITY, HOW IS THE REPUTATION OF YOUR SCHOOL?

- Considerably above average
- Above average
- Average
- Below average
- Considerably below average

---Page Break---

HOW MUCH PRESSURE DO YOU, AS THE [PIPED TEXT WITH LEADERSHIP FUNCTION], FEEL TO OBTAIN OR MAINTAIN A SUFFICIENT NUMBER OF STUDENTS AT YOUR SCHOOL?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all" and 7 indicates "An extreme amount".

- Not at all 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- An extreme amount 7

---Page Break---

DOES YOUR SCHOOL PARTICIPATE IN ANY COLLABORATIVE PROJECTS, NETWORKS OR REGULAR ACTIVITIES WITH OTHER SCHOOLS?

- Yes, please indicate how many schools you collaborate with: _____
- No

---Page Break---

Display This Question if Collaboration with other schools = Yes

YOU SAID THAT YOUR SCHOOL COLLABORATES WITH [N. OF COLLABORATING SCHOOLS] SCHOOLS. HOW MANY OF THEM ARE:

As categories are not exclusive, in each row you may indicate up to [n. of collaborating schools] schools.

Neighbouring schools: ____

Schools that have a similar pedagogical approach: ____

Only if not public: Schools of the same religious order (if applicable): ____

All cases, except Spanish ones: Schools that have the same [administrator/school owner].

Other, please specify: ____

---Page Break---

Display This Question if Collaboration with other schools = Yes

HOW OFTEN DOES YOUR SCHOOL PARTICIPATE IN COLLABORATIVE PROJECTS, NETWORKS OR REGULAR ACTIVITIES WITH OTHER SCHOOLS?

- Monthly or more than monthly
- More than once a year but less than monthly
- Once a year
- Less than once a year

WHY DOES YOUR SCHOOL PARTICIPATE IN THESE COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES WITH OTHER SCHOOLS?

(Multiple answers possible)

- To share knowledge and experiences
- To establish common ways to assess and evaluate our students
- To develop a common pedagogical plan
- To increase the visibility of our schools
- To influence local and/or national policy making
- Other, please specify: _____

---Page Break---

WHO MAKES THE DECISIONS CONCERNING THIS SCHOOL IN THE FOLLOWING DOMAINS?

Please select all the actors that have some room for decision-making in the following domains.

(List of domains)

- Budget allocation
- Selection of school principals
- Selection of new teachers
- All cases, except Norway: Teachers' salary increases/Teachers' promotion
- All cases, except Norway: Students' admission into the school
- All cases: Curriculum adjustment (curricular objectives and/or contents) The Netherlands: curriculum development
- Choice of textbooks and teaching materials
- Content of in-service training
- Assessment of teaching quality
- Teaching methods
- Students' assessment criteria and procedures
- The Netherlands: Choice of eindtoets
- The Netherlands: Choice of LVS
- The raising and use of private funds

[List of case-specific relevant actors from Ministry of Education, local and regional actors to school actors].

I do not know

---Page Break---

SOME SCHOOLS ORGANIZE INSTRUCTION DIFFERENTLY FOR STUDENTS WITH DIFFERENT ABILITIES. WHAT IS YOUR SCHOOL POLICY REGARDING THIS?

Students are grouped by ability:

- For all subjects
- For some subjects
- For some activities or projects
- Never

---Page Break---

Display This Question if Ability grouping = For some subjects

FOR WHICH SUBJECTS ARE STUDENTS GROUPED BY ABILITY?

(Multiple choice possible)

[Dropdown menu with case-specific subjects]

---Page Break---

Display This Question if Ability grouping = For all subjects Or If Subjects of Ability grouping Is Greater Than 1

THESE GROUPS...

- ...are always the same
- ...change according to the subject

---Page Break---

TO WHAT EXTENT DO THE FOLLOWING SOURCES/PRACTICES PROVIDE USEFUL INFORMATION AND GUIDANCE TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF TEACHING IN YOUR SCHOOL?

	None at all	A little	Some	A lot	Absolutely	Not applicable. We do not use/do it
Feedback from colleagues and/or mentors	☐					
Feedback from parents or guardians/students	☐					
<i>Chile:</i> Feedback from inspector's service	☐					
National test results and/or discussions around them	☐					
<i>The Netherlands:</i> Student monitoring system (LVS)	☐					
Classroom exam results. <i>In the Netherlands:</i> Classroom test results (such as method tests)	☐					
<i>Chile:</i> Results of the teacher evaluation	☐					
In-service training	☐					
Publications by experts (books, articles, internet, etc.)	☐					
External consultancy (private providers)	☐					
<i>Chile, the Netherlands & Norway:</i> Students' and/or parents' surveys	☐					
<i>Chile:</i> Feedback from the Supervisor of the Ministry of Education	☐					
<i>Chile:</i> Feedback from the Quality Agency	☐					
<i>Norway:</i> Medarbejderundersøkelse	☐					
<i>Chile:</i> Feedback and supervision from the Sostenedor	☐					
<i>Chile:</i> Results of SEPA test	☐					
<i>The Netherlands:</i> Feedback from the school board	☐					
Other, please specify:	☐					

---Page Break---

THE FOLLOWING QUESTIONS WILL FOCUS ON THE [NATIONAL TEST] AND ON THE DATA THAT IT GENERATES.

All cases except Norway

IMAGINE THAT YOUR SCHOOL HAS OBTAINED BAD RESULTS IN THE LAST STANDARDISED TEST. YOU WANT TO IMPROVE THE RESULTS FOR THE COMING YEARS. WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING STRATEGIES WOULD YOU ADOPT?

When you answer, consider that your school situation is the same as it is now: your colleagues are the same, the school inspector/s is/are the same, your students are the same, so are their parents.

Even if you aren't entirely sure or if in your context some actions are not possible, please indicate which of the two you would prefer.

[Two potential strategies with a randomized selection of the following features are presented. The order of dimension is also randomized]

DIMENSION	[FEATURES]
Educational approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continue with current teaching practices Modify the curriculum according to the competence tested Dedicate more class time to practice for the test
Staff management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Make no change in the management of the staff Provide professional development to the teachers whose students got bad results in the test Try to place teachers whose students got bad results in grades not affected by the test
Students' targeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do not target students with any specific profile Encourage parents of high-performing students to enrol their children in your school Dissuade parents of low-performing students to enrol their children in your school
Policy for student admission in case of oversubscription	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Admit students through a lottery system Admit students based on criteria such as proximity, siblings already at the school, and having social or special needs Admit students based on their reports from previous school and/or interviews with parents

WHICH OF THE TWO STRATEGIES WOULD YOU ADOPT?

- Strategy A
- Strategy B

---Page Break---

ON A SCALE OF 1 TO 7, WHERE 1 INDICATES THAT YOU WOULD NEVER FOLLOW STRATEGY A, AND 7 THAT YOU WOULD FOLLOW THIS STRATEGY WITHOUT A DOUBT, PLEASE INDICATE TO WHAT EXTENT YOU WOULD FOLLOW STRATEGY A:

- 7 I would follow Strategy A without a doubt
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 I would never follow Strategy A

ON A SCALE OF 1 TO 7, WHERE 1 INDICATES THAT YOU WOULD NEVER FOLLOW STRATEGY B, AND 7 THAT YOU WOULD FOLLOW THIS STRATEGY WITHOUT A DOUBT, PLEASE INDICATE TO WHAT EXTENT YOU WOULD FOLLOW STRATEGY B:

- 7 I would follow Strategy B without a doubt
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 I would never follow Strategy B

---Page Break---

AND BETWEEN THESE TWO STRATEGIES?

[Two further potential strategies with a randomized selection of the features are presented. The order of dimension is also randomized]

WHICH OF THE TWO STRATEGIES WOULD YOU ADOPT?

- Strategy A
- Strategy B

---Page Break---

ON A SCALE OF 1 TO 7, WHERE 1 INDICATES THAT YOU WOULD NEVER FOLLOW STRATEGY A, AND 7 THAT YOU WOULD FOLLOW THIS STRATEGY WITHOUT A DOUBT, PLEASE INDICATE TO WHAT EXTENT YOU WOULD FOLLOW STRATEGY A:

- 7 I would follow Strategy A without a doubt
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 I would never follow Strategy A

ON A SCALE OF 1 TO 7, WHERE 1 INDICATES THAT YOU WOULD NEVER FOLLOW STRATEGY B, AND 7 THAT YOU WOULD FOLLOW THIS STRATEGY WITHOUT A DOUBT, PLEASE INDICATE TO WHAT EXTENT YOU WOULD FOLLOW STRATEGY B:

- 7 I would follow Strategy B without a doubt
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 I would never follow Strategy B

---Page Break---

	Not at all/None at all	A little	Some	A lot	Completely
case is not Norway					
IN YOUR SCHOOL HAS [NATIONAL TEST] LED TO A REDISTRIBUTION OF RESOURCES (TIME, PERSONNEL, AND BUDGET) IN FAVOR OF THE SUBJECT AREAS AND COMPETENCES THAT ARE TESTED?	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
TO WHAT EXTENT HAS THE EXISTENCE OF LEARNING STANDARDS INFLUENCED THE PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH OF THIS SCHOOL?	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
IN YOUR SCHOOL, TO WHAT EXTENT IS [NATIONAL TEST] TAKEN INTO ACCOUNT WHEN TAKING DECISIONS ABOUT CURRICULAR CONTENT?	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
For Norway					
IN YOUR SCHOOL HAS [NATIONAL TEST] LED TO A REDISTRIBUTION OF RESOURCES (TIME, PERSONNEL, AND BUDGET) IN FAVOR OF COMPETENCES THAT ARE TESTED?	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

IN YOUR SCHOOL, WHAT ARE THE RESULTS OF [NATIONAL TEST] USED FOR?

(Multiple choice possible)

- To define and monitor our school improvement plan.
- To identify students with a need for more support and follow-up
- To assess teachers' work.
- To take decisions about professional development activities for teachers
- To inform parents about the school achievement
- To group students (by achievement) for instructional purposes
- To reward well-performing teachers
- To compare our performance with that of other schools
- To adjust the curriculum accordingly

case is not Norway

- To report among the teaching staff

case = The Netherlands Or Catalonia and Madrid (secondary schools)

- To help stream students into further education
- To build the school's reputation

---Page Break---

IN THIS SCHOOL DO YOU CONSIDER IT DIFFICULT TO TRANSFORM NATIONAL TEST DATA INTO CONCRETE MEASURES/ACTIONS TO IMPROVE TEACHING?

- Absolutely
- A lot
- To some extent
- A little
- Not at all

---Page Break---

Display Question if Capacity to use the data is not Not at all

WHAT FACTORS COULD EXPLAIN THESE DIFFICULTIES?

- The interpretation of the data requires statistical competences
- Data are not provided at the student level
- Data do tell me anything I did not know before
- The report is not clear
- Lack of time to analyse/use the data
- Data/the report are not accessible
- Other, please specify: _____

---Page Break---

HAVE YOU EVER PARTICIPATED IN ANY TRAINING ACTIVITIES FOCUSING ON HOW TO ANALYZE AND USE NATIONAL TEST RESULTS FOR SCHOOL IMPROVEMENT PURPOSES?

- Yes
- No

---Page Break---

	No, never	Yes, it has been recommended	Yes, it has been instructed
<p><i>Catalonia, Chile, Madrid, The Netherlands & Norway (public schools)</i></p> <p>HAS THE [SCHOOL OWNER/NL: SCHOOL BOARD] RECOMMENDED OR INSTRUCTED THAT TEACHING SHOULD BE ADJUSTED TO THE ACHIEVEMENT OF THE EVALUABLE LEARNING STANDARDS?</p>	☐	☐	☐
<p><i>Catalonia, Chile, Madrid, The Netherlands & Norway (public schools)</i></p> <p>HAS THE [SCHOOL OWNER/NL: SCHOOL BOARD] RECOMMENDED OR INSTRUCTED THAT STUDENTS SHOULD PRACTICE FOR [NATIONAL TEST]?</p>	☐	☐	☐
<p><i>Catalonia, Chile, Madrid & Norway (not public schools)</i></p> <p>HAS THE [SCHOOL BOARD] RECOMMENDED OR INSTRUCTED THAT TEACHING SHOULD BE ADJUSTED TO THE ACHIEVEMENT OF THE EVALUABLE LEARNING STANDARDS?</p>	☐	☐	☐
<p><i>Catalonia, Chile, Madrid & Norway (not public schools)</i></p> <p>HAS THE [SCHOOL BOARD] RECOMMENDED OR INSTRUCTED THAT STUDENTS SHOULD PRACTICE FOR [NATIONAL TEST]?</p>	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

Display This Question if case is Chile, The Netherlands, Catalonia (not public schools) & Madrid (not public schools)

THE ROLE OF SCHOOL INSPECTORS REGARDING THE [NATIONAL TEST] IS CENTERED ON:

(Multiple answer possible)

- Supervising the application of the school targets/plan
- Giving information about test implementation procedures

The Netherlands

- Delivering the LVS school results to the schools
- Delivering the results of the national test to the schools
- Giving advice on how to strengthen the school performance in [national test]
- Observing teaching and giving feedback
- Other, please specify: _____

---Page Break---

IN YOUR OPINION, HOW MUCH IMPORTANCE IS GIVEN TO THE [NATIONAL TEST] IN THE CURRENT PUBLIC EDUCATIONAL DEBATE?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all important" and 7 indicates "Extremely important".

- Not at all important 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- Extremely important 7

---Page Break---

TO YOUR KNOWLEDGE, DO THE RESULTS OF [NATIONAL TEST] HAVE ANY KIND OF CONSEQUENCES (ECONOMIC, WORK-RELATED, REPUTATIONAL, ETC.) FOR ANY OF THE FOLLOWING ACTORS?

(Multiple answers possible)

- For the principal
- For teachers
- All cases, except The Netherlands: For students
- Norway: For the school owner
- For the school
- The Netherlands: For the school board
- Norway (not public schools): For the school board
- No consequences
- I do not know

---Page Break---

Display Question if Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom is not No consequences

And Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom is not I do not know

WHAT ARE THE CONSEQUENCES OF THE [NATIONAL TEST]?

(Multiple choice possible)

Display Question if Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom = For the principal

FOR THE PRINCIPAL:

- Salary bonus
- Increases or decreases of the principal's salary
- The principal can be withdrawn from his/her position
- Impact on professional reputation
- Other, please specify: _____
- I do not know the exact consequences

Display Question if Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom = For teachers

FOR TEACHERS

- Salary bonus
 - Teachers' tenure/promotion decisions
 - Salary increases or decreases
 - Provision of professional development (training and attendance to conferences, mentoring, individual/collaborative research)
 - Impact on professional reputation
 - Other, please specify: _____
- I do not know the exact consequences

Display Question if Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom = For students

FOR STUDENTS

- Student grade promotion or graduation
 - Rewards for students
 - Other, please specify: _____
- I do not know the exact consequences

Display Question if Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom = For the school

FOR THE SCHOOL:

- *Chile & The Netherlands:* The school is more closely monitored by the ministry
 - School closure
 - *All cases, except Norway:* Award of a collective salary bonus
 - Impact on the school reputation
 - The educational authority provides extra support/resources to the school
 - *Catalonia & Madrid:* The school is more closely monitored by the inspectorate
 - *Chile:* The school is more closely monitored by the agency of quality
 - *Norway (not public schools):* The school is more closely monitored by the school board
 - *Norway (public schools):* The school is more closely monitored by the school owner
 - *The Netherlands:* The school is more closely monitored by the school board
 - Other, please specify: _____
- I do not know the exact consequences

---Page Break---

HOW MUCH PRESSURE DO YOU, AS THE [PIPED TEXT WITH LEADERSHIP FUNCTION] IN THIS SCHOOL, FEEL TO GET GOOD RESULTS IN [NATIONAL TEST]?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "None at all" and 7 indicates "An extreme amount".

- None at all 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- An extreme amount 7

---Page Break---

TO WHAT EXTENT DOES THIS PRESSURE COME FROM THE FOLLOWING ACTORS?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all" and 7 indicates "Extremely".

Ministry of Education – Federal/Central authority

For Chile: Agency of Quality

For Chile: "Superintendence"

For Norway: Regional Authority

For the Spanish cases: Autonomic authority

For Chilean public schools, Norway and the NL:

Municipal authority

For the NL: School board

For the NL and the Spanish cases: The inspectorate

For not public schools, except for the NL: School board

In the TQ: Principal and/or other members of the leadership team

In Chile and the Spanish cases: School council

In the PQ: Teachers

In the TQ: Other teachers

Parents

The media

Self-imposed pressure

Other, please specify: _____

For each option:

- 7 An extreme amount
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 None at all

---Page Break---

WE WOULD LIKE TO KNOW YOUR OPINIONS ON [NATIONAL TEST] AND OTHER IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF THE SCHOOL ORGANISATION.

DO YOU THINK THAT A SCHOOL'S [NATIONAL TEST] RESULTS INFLUENCE ITS REPUTATION?

- Not at all
- A little
- To some extent
- A lot
- Absolutely

---Page Break---

TO WHAT EXTENT DO YOU THINK THAT IT IS FAIR...

	Very unfair	Unfair	Fair	Very fair
... to measure the quality of a school based on [national test] results?	☐	☐	☐	☐
... to publicly disseminate [national test] results in the media and/or internet?	☐	☐	☐	☐
... that schools with different characteristics are compared on the basis of their [national test] results?	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

IN YOUR OPINION, TO WHAT EXTENT DOES A SCHOOL'S SCORE IN [NATIONAL TEST] REFLECT THE EFFORTS AND ABILITY OF THE INDIVIDUAL TEACHERS?

- Completely
- A lot
- To some extent
- A little
- Not at all

---Page Break---

TO WHAT EXTENT DO YOU AGREE OR DISAGREE WITH THE FOLLOWING STATEMENTS?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Preparation for [national test] takes too much time away from more important activities in the school	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The content of [national test] tells us what the school's priorities are	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The results of [national test] do not provide useful information on student learning	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
A good teacher can be recognized by his/her students' results in [national test]	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The results of [national test] do not adequately represent what students have learned and can do	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

IN YOUR OPINION, FOR A SCHOOL TO WORK WELL, WHO SHOULD BE RESPONSIBLE OF THE FOLLOWING DOMAINS?

(Multiple answers possible)

- | | |
|---|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Budget allocation Selection of school principals Selection of new teachers All cases, except Norway: Teachers' salary increases/Teachers' promotion All cases, except Norway: Students' admission into the school All cases, except the NL: Curriculum adjustment (curricular objectives and/or content) For the NL: Curriculum development Choice of textbooks and teaching materials Content of in-service training Assessment of teaching quality Teaching methods Students' assessment criteria and procedures For the NL: Choice of eindtoets For the NL: Choice of LVS The raising and use of private funds | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Educational authorities/administration ▪ Principal and/or leadership team ▪ All cases, except Norway and the NL: School council ▪ For the NL: Medezeggenschapsraad ▪ Teachers |
|---|---|

---Page Break---

NOW WE HAVE A FEW QUESTIONS ON THE USE OF EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES AND SERVICES DELIVERED BY PRIVATE COMPANIES IN THIS SCHOOL.

IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS, HOW OFTEN HAVE YOU USED ANY OF THESE EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES DELIVERED BY PRIVATE COMPANIES (INCLUDING PUBLISHERS)?

	Never	Once	More than once but less than monthly	Once a month	More than once a month
Lesson plans (online or paper)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Test preparation resources	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Consultancy/training services on instructional improvement	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
<i>case is not Norway</i>					
Edu-marketing/students' recruitment's services	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

Display This Question if any use of educational resources provided by private companies

WHO HAVE BEEN THE MAIN AGENTS ACQUIRING THESE RESOURCES FOR THE SCHOOL?

(Multiple choice possible)

For each resource previously selected:

- Education department
- Norway (public schools), Chile (public schools) & The Netherlands: Municipality
- The Netherlands: School board
- Norway, Chile, Catalonia & Madrid (all not public schools): Private school owner/board
- The school
- Personally (bought with my own money)
- Other

---Page Break---

Display This Question if more than 1 agent acquiring

Approximately, what percentage of the school's budget goes to the acquisition of educational services and products delivered to the school by private companies (including publishers)?

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

Display This Question if any use of educational resources provided by private companies

HOW DO YOU RATE THE VALUE FOR MONEY OF THE RESOURCES THAT PRIVATE COMPANIES (INCLUDING PUBLISHERS) DELIVER?

- Very bad
- Bad
- Good
- Very good

---Page Break---

WE WOULD LIKE TO ASK YOU SOME QUESTIONS ABOUT YOU AND YOUR JOB.

HOW MANY HOURS A WEEK ARE YOU EMPLOYED IN THIS SCHOOL?

[Dropdown menu with n. of hours]

---Page Break---

Display This Question if Leadership function in the school is not Other, please specify:

IN A NORMAL SCHOOL WEEK, WHAT PERCENTAGE OF YOUR WORKING HOURS DO YOU APPROXIMATELY SPEND ON EACH OF THE FOLLOWING TASKS IN YOUR ROLE AS [PIPED TEXT WITH LEADERSHIP FUNCTION] IN THIS SCHOOL?

Sum must be 100%.

- Administrative management (budget, human resources management, etc.)
- Pedagogical management (curriculum, pedagogical planning, etc.)
- Producing reports and the school plan, filling-in forms, uploading information into online platforms, etc.
- Interactions with parents/guardians
- Analysis of test results and discussion of students' and school's performance
- Other, please specify:

---Page Break---

IDEALLY, IN A NORMAL SCHOOL WEEK, WHAT PERCENTAGE OF YOUR WORKING HOURS SHOULD YOU BE ABLE TO SPEND ON THESE TASKS TO CARRY OUT YOUR PROFESSIONAL RESPONSIBILITIES IN THE BEST POSSIBLE WAY?

Sum must 100%.

- Administrative management (budget, human resources management, etc.)
- Pedagogical management (curriculum, pedagogical planning, etc.)
- Producing reports and the school plan, filling-in forms, uploading information into online platforms, etc.
- Interactions with parents/guardians
- Analysis of test results and discussion of students' and school's performance
- Other, please specify:

---Page Break---

HOW OFTEN DURING THE YEAR DO YOU WORK MORE THAN YOUR CONTRACTED WEEKLY HOURS?

- Never
- Seldom (very few weeks a year)
- Occasionally (some weeks a year)
- Frequently (many weeks a year)
- All or almost all weeks

---Page Break---

TO WHAT EXTENT DO YOU AGREE OR DISAGREE WITH THE FOLLOWING STATEMENTS?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
I would like to move to another school if it were possible	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I enjoy working at this school	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I would recommend my school as a good place to work	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I wonder whether it would have been better to choose another profession	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I regret that I decided to become a [Piped text with leadership function]	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
All in all, I am satisfied with my job	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
If I could decide again, I would still choose to work as a [Piped text with leadership function]	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

IS YOUR CURRENT CONTRACT IN THIS SCHOOL A...

- Permanent contract
- For the NL and Norway: Fixed term contract, more than 3 years
- Fixed term contract, 1-3 years
- Fixed term contract, less than 1 year
- For Chile: "Contracto a honorarios"

Display This Question if case = Catalonia Or Madrid And Leadership function in the school is not principal Or If case is the Netherlands

IS YOUR EMPLOYMENT IN THIS SCHOOL:

- Full time
- Part time

---Page Break---

Display Question if Type of contract = Part time

ARE YOU CURRENTLY WORKING IN ANY OTHER SCHOOL?

- No
- Yes, in a public school
- Yes, in a private school
- Yes, in an independent publicly funded school

---Page Break---

ARE YOU CURRENTLY TEACHING?

- Yes
- No

---Page Break---

*Display This Question if case is not The Netherlands And If currently teaching = Yes***WHICH SUBJECT(S) ARE YOU TEACHING THIS SCHOOL YEAR?**

- *[Case-specific list of subjects]*
- Other, please specify: ____

---Page Break---

*Display This Question if currently teaching = Yes***WHICH GRADE(S) ARE YOU TEACHING THIS SCHOOL YEAR?***[Case-specific list of subjects]*

---Page Break---

WHAT YEAR DID YOU START WORKING IN THE EDUCATION SECTOR?*[Dropdown menu with years]***WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING DEGREES/CERTIFICATES DO YOU HOLD?***(Multiple answers possible)**[Context-sensitive list of degrees/certificates]*

---Page Break---

*Display Question if more than 1 degree/certificate were selected***WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING DEGREE/S HAS/HAVE GIVEN YOU THE RIGHT TO TEACH?***[List of previously selected degrees/certificate]*

---Page Break---

*Display Question if degrees/certificates is Equal to 1***IN WHAT YEAR/S DID YOU COMPLETE THIS DEGREE?***[Dropdown menu with years]*

---Page Break---

*Display Question if case is not Norway***ARE YOU A MEMBER OF A PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATION (COLLEGIAL OR PEDAGOGICAL) OR DO YOU TAKE PART IN A CAMPAIGN OR PLATFORM IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION?**

- Yes
- No

ARE YOU A MEMBER OF A TEACHER UNION?

- Yes
- No
- Norway: I prefer not to answer

---Page Break---

Display Question if Professional association membership = Yes

PLEASE INDICATE THE NAME OF THE ASSOCIATION/S OR PLATFORMS/CAMPAIGNS YOU ARE A MEMBER OF:
[Context-sensitive list of associations/platforms/campaigns]

Display Question if Union membership = Yes

WHICH UNION ARE YOU A MEMBER OF?
(Context-sensitive list of teachers' unions)

---Page Break---

BEFORE ENDING THIS SURVEY, WE WOULD LIKE TO KNOW YOUR OPINION ON A FEW NON-EDUCATIONAL MATTERS.

TO WHAT EXTENT DO YOU AGREE OR DISAGREE WITH THE FOLLOWING STATEMENTS?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
The government should take measures to reduce differences in income levels	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Workers need strong trade unions to protect their working conditions and wages	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The less the government intervenes in the economy, the better it is for the country	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR PARTICIPATING IN OUR SURVEY!

WOULD YOU BE INTERESTED IN THE RESULTS OF THIS STUDY?

- Yes, I would like to receive a report with the main findings of this study
- Yes, I would like to receive an invitation to the devolution seminar, organized in [city] on [date]
- No

WOULD YOU LIKE TO PARTICIPATE IN THE PRIZE DRAW OF [SPECIFY PRIZE]?

- Yes
- No

---Page Break---

Display Question if one of the previous questions is = Yes

PLEASE PROVIDE AN E-MAIL ADDRESS THAT WE CAN USE TO INFORM YOU IN THE FUTURE ABOUT THE RESULTS OF THIS STUDY AND/OR ABOUT THE RESULTS OF THE PRIZE DRAW:

---Page Break---

IS THERE ANYTHING ELSE YOU WOULD LIKE TO COMMENT ON WITH REGARD TO QUESTIONS OR THEMES THAT YOU THINK SHOULD BE EXPLORED FURTHER?

Teacher questionnaire

The REFORMED team cordially invites you to participate in this survey focusing on schools' organizational dynamics, educational practices, and teaching methods, as well as teachers' and school leaders' opinions on and experiences with recent educational reforms.

Your participation will make an invaluable contribution to our research!

The survey will take around **30 minutes** to complete.

The data collected from the survey will be anonymized and securely stored. This study follows the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The survey is completely voluntary and you may opt out at any time. By completing and submitting the survey, you give informed consent to participate in the study.

Many thanks for your collaboration!

If you have any questions about this project, do not hesitate to contact us at [e-mail address of case responsible]

---Page Break---

WHICH SUBJECT(S) ARE YOU TEACHING THIS SCHOOL YEAR?

- [Case-specific list of subjects]
- Other, please specify: ____

---Page Break---

WHICH GRADE(S) ARE YOU TEACHING THIS SCHOOL YEAR?

- [Case-specific list of subjects]

---Page Break---

Display Question if case is not Norway

HOW MANY HOURS A WEEK ARE YOU EMPLOYED IN THIS SCHOOL?

[Dropdown menu with n. of hours]

---Page Break---

WHAT YEAR DID YOU START WORKING AS A TEACHER IN THIS SCHOOL?

[Dropdown menu with years]

- Yes
- No

IN THE PAST HAVE YOU EVER BEEN THE PRINCIPAL OR PART OF THE MANAGEMENT TEAM IN THIS OR ANY OTHER SCHOOL?

- Yes
- No

---Page Break---

Display Question if Previous experience as a teacher = Yes Or if Previous experience as a "principal"/"other member of management team" overall = Yes

WHAT YEAR DID YOU START WORKING IN THE EDUCATION SECTOR?

[Dropdown menu with years]

PLEASE INDICATE YOUR GENDER:

- Male
- Female
- Other

PLEASE INDICATE YOUR AGE (IN DIGITS):

---Page Break---

DO YOU HAVE A LEADERSHIP OR COORDINATION ROLE SUCH AS [PUT HERE CONTEXT-SENSITIVE EXAMPLE OF LEADERSHIP/COORDINATION ROLES]?

- Yes
- No

---Page Break---

Display Question if Any leadership role = Yes

WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING OPTIONS BEST DESCRIBES YOUR LEADERSHIP/COORDINATION ROLE IN THIS SCHOOL?

Select all that apply

- [Context-sensitive list with leadership/coordination roles]
- Other, please specify: ____

---Page Break---

WE WOULD LIKE TO KNOW MORE ABOUT YOUR TEACHING METHODS AND CLASSROOM PRACTICES.

ON AVERAGE, HOW OFTEN DO YOU DO THE FOLLOWING WHEN YOU TEACH?

	NEVER	SELDOM (once a month)	OCCASIONALLY (several times a month)	FREQUENTLY (several times a week)	IN EVERY CLASS
Students are given a lecture-style presentation	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Students work individually	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Students work in groups	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Students complete a test or quiz	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Students are involved in debates and discussions	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

HOW OFTEN DOES EACH OF THE FOLLOWING HAPPEN IN YOUR CLASS THROUGHOUT THE SCHOOL YEAR?

Please mark one choice in each row.

	NEVER	SELDOM (once a month)	OCCASIONALLY (several times a month)	FREQUENTLY (several times a week)	IN EVERY CLASS
I explicitly state the learning goals at the beginning of the activities	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I present a summary of recently learned content	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I present the lesson units in an organized and sequenced manner	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I ask questions to check students' understanding	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I check students' exercise books or homework and provide feedback	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I provide feedback during class about how students are working	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

HOW OFTEN DOES EACH OF THE FOLLOWING HAPPEN IN YOUR CLASS THROUGHOUT THE SCHOOL YEAR?

Please mark one choice in each row.

	NEVER	SELDOM (once a month)	OCCASIONALLY (several times a month)	FREQUENTLY (several times a week)	IN EVERY CLASS
I encourage students to solve problems in more than one way	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I expect students to decide and explain their own procedures for solving complex problems	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I ask students to relate what they are learning to problems from daily life	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I ask students to explicitly think about and explain what they are learning	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Students work on projects that require at least one week to complete	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Students work in groups to come up with a joint solution to a problem or task	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Students use ICT (information and communication technology) for projects or class work	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

ON AVERAGE, HOW OFTEN DO YOU DO THE FOLLOWING IN YOUR CLASS?

	NEVER	SELDOM (once a month)	OCCASIONALLY (Several times a month)	FREQUENTLY (several times a week)	IN EVERY CLASS
I create groups of students with similar abilities	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I create groups with mixed abilities	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I give different work to the students who have learning difficulties	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I give different work to the advanced students	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

IN A NORMAL SCHOOL WEEK, WHAT PERCENTAGE OF YOUR WORKING HOURS DO YOU APPROXIMATELY SPEND ON EACH OF THE FOLLOWING TASKS?

Sum must be 100%.

- _____ Teaching in the classroom
- _____ Preparing lessons, marking student work
- _____ Discussing and sharing professional ideas and tips with colleagues
- _____ Interactions with parents/guardians
- _____ Producing reports, filling in forms, uploading information onto online platforms, as requested by the management
- _____ Professional learning/development activities
- _____ Other, please specify:

---Page Break---

IDEALLY, IN A NORMAL SCHOOL WEEK, WHAT PERCENTAGE OF YOUR WORKING HOURS SHOULD YOU BE ABLE TO SPEND ON THESE TASKS TO CARRY OUT YOUR PROFESSIONAL RESPONSIBILITIES IN THE BEST POSSIBLE WAY?

Sum must be 100%.

- _____ Teaching in the classroom
- _____ Preparing lessons, marking student work
- _____ Discussing and sharing professional ideas and tips with colleagues
- _____ Interactions with parents/guardians
- _____ Producing reports, filling in forms, uploading information onto online platforms, as requested by the management
- _____ Professional learning/development activities
- _____ Other, please specify:

---Page Break---

HOW OFTEN DURING THE YEAR DO YOU WORK MORE THAN YOUR WEEKLY CONTRACTED HOURS?

- Never
- Seldom (very few weeks a year)
- Occasionally (some weeks a year)
- Frequently (many weeks a year)
- All or almost all weeks

---Page Break---

**BELOW WE PRESENT YOU WITH TWO PAIRS OF SCHOOL THAT DIFFER IN SOME ASPECTS.
 PLEASE INDICATE WHICH SCHOOL YOU WOULD PREFER TO WORK IN, IF YOU COULD CHOOSE ONE OF THEM.**

*The scenarios are hypothetical and may not correspond to the real conditions existing in your context.
 Even if you aren't entirely sure, please indicate which of the two schools you would prefer.*

[Two potential schools with a randomized selection of the following features are presented. The order of dimension is also randomized]

DIMENSION	[FEATURES]
Type of students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Advantaged (easy-to-teach students) ● Mixed ability (diversity of learning paces) ● Struggling (hard-to-teach students)
Type of assessment of teaching quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assessed on the basis of students' national test results ● Assessed on the basis of classroom observation ● "Assessed on the basis of teacher's portfolio"
Goal-setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Goals are well defined and well communicated ● Goals are not always clear and well communicated ● No performance goals are set
Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The principal is engaged and very supportive ● Parents are engaged and very supportive" ● The other teachers are engaged and very supportive
Rewards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yearly salary bonus for individual teachers according to teaching assessment results ● Yearly budgetary rewards for the school according to teaching assessments results at the school level ● No salary bonuses or budgetary rewards attached to the teaching assessment

WHICH OF THE TWO SCHOOLS WOULD YOU PREFER?

- School A
- School B

---Page Break---

ON A SCALE OF 1 TO 7, WHERE 1 INDICATES THAT YOU WOULD NEVER WORK IN SCHOOL A, AND 7 THAT YOU WOULD WORK THERE WITHOUT A DOUBT, PLEASE INDICATE TO WHAT EXTENT YOU WOULD WORK IN SCHOOL A IF YOU COULD CHOOSE:

- 7 I would work in School A without a doubt
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 I would never choose to work in School A

ON A SCALE OF 1 TO 7, WHERE 1 INDICATES THAT YOU WOULD NEVER WORK IN SCHOOL B, AND 7 THAT YOU WOULD WORK THERE WITHOUT A DOUBT, PLEASE INDICATE TO WHAT EXTENT YOU WOULD WORK IN SCHOOL B IF YOU COULD CHOOSE:

- 7 I would work in School B without a doubt
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 I would never choose to work in School B

---Page Break---

AND BETWEEN THESE TWO SCHOOLS?

[Two further potential schools with a randomized selection of the features are presented. The order of dimension is also randomized]

WHICH OF THE TWO SCHOOLS WOULD YOU PREFER?

- School A
- School B

---Page Break---

ON A SCALE OF 1 TO 7, WHERE 1 INDICATES THAT YOU WOULD NEVER WORK IN SCHOOL A, AND 7 THAT YOU WOULD WORK THERE WITHOUT A DOUBT, PLEASE INDICATE TO WHAT EXTENT YOU WOULD WORK IN SCHOOL A IF YOU COULD CHOOSE:

- 7 I would work in School A without a doubt
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 I would never choose to work in School A

ON A SCALE OF 1 TO 7, WHERE 1 INDICATES THAT YOU WOULD NEVER WORK IN SCHOOL B, AND 7 THAT YOU WOULD WORK THERE WITHOUT A DOUBT, PLEASE INDICATE TO WHAT EXTENT YOU WOULD WORK IN SCHOOL B IF YOU COULD CHOOSE:

- 7 I would work in School B without a doubt
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 I would never choose to work in School B

---Page Break---

NOW WE WOULD LIKE TO KNOW MORE ABOUT THE SCHOOL CONTEXT WHERE YOU WORK.

IN THIS SCHOOL, HOW OFTEN DO YOU...

	Never	Seldom	Occasionally	Frequently
...discuss teaching strategies and students' learning issues with colleagues?	☐	☐	☐	☐
...share and/or develop instructional material(s) with your colleagues?	☐	☐	☐	☐

HOW MANY COLLEAGUES AT THIS SCHOOL DO YOU FEEL YOU SHARE YOUR VIEWS ON WHAT THE CENTRAL MISSION OF THE SCHOOL SHOULD BE?

	With no one	With a minority of them	With approximately half of them	With the majority of them	With everyone
	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

WHEN YOU FEEL DOWN ABOUT YOUR TEACHING AND/OR YOUR STUDENTS, HOW MANY COLLEAGUES IN THIS SCHOOL CAN YOU COUNT ON FOR SUPPORT?

	On no one	On a minority of them	On approximately half of them	On the majority of them	On everyone
	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

TO WHAT EXTENT DO TEACHERS IN THIS SCHOOL FEEL THEY CAN CONSULT THE PRINCIPAL/MANAGEMENT TEAM WHEN THEY HAVE A PROBLEM?

Not at all A little To some extent A lot Absolutely

-

TO WHAT EXTENT DOES THE PRINCIPAL/MANAGEMENT TEAM SUPPORT TEACHERS WHEN THEY NEED IT?

-

TO WHAT EXTENT IS THERE A COOPERATIVE EFFORT AMONG THE TEACHING STAFF IN YOUR SCHOOL?

-

---Page Break---

WHO MAKES THE DECISIONS CONCERNING THIS SCHOOL IN THE FOLLOWING DOMAINS?

Please select all the actors that have some room for decision-making in the following domains.

(List of domains)

- Budget allocation
- Selection of school principals
- Selection of new teachers
- All cases, except Norway: Teachers' salary increases/Teachers' promotion
- All cases, except Norway: Students' admission into the school
- All cases: Curriculum adjustment (curricular objectives and/or contents) The Netherlands: curriculum development
- Choice of textbooks and teaching materials
- Content of in-service training
- Assessment of teaching quality
- Teaching methods
- Students' assessment criteria and procedures
- The Netherlands: Choice of eindtoets
- The Netherlands: Choice of LVS
- The raising and use of private funds

[List of case-specific relevant actors from Ministry of Education, local and regional actors to school actors].

I do not know

---Page Break---

TO WHAT EXTENT DO TEACHERS IN THIS SCHOOL ARE ENCOURAGED BY THE MANAGEMENT TEAM TO GIVE THEIR OPINIONS AND SUGGESTIONS ON IMPORTANT SCHOOL ISSUES?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all" and 7 indicates "Absolutely".

- Not at all 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- Absolutely 7

---Page Break---

TO WHAT EXTENT DO THE FOLLOWING SOURCES/PRACTICES PROVIDE USEFUL INFORMATION AND GUIDANCE TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF TEACHING IN YOUR SCHOOL?

	None at all	A little	Some	A lot	Absolutely	Not applicable. We do not use/do it
Feedback from colleagues and/or mentors	☐					
Feedback from parents or guardians/students	☐					
<i>Chile:</i> Feedback from inspector's service	☐					
National test results and/or discussions around them	☐					
<i>The Netherlands:</i> Student monitoring system (LVS)	☐					
Classroom exam results. <i>In the Netherlands:</i> Classroom test results (such as method tests)	☐					
<i>Chile:</i> Results of the teacher evaluation	☐					
In-service training	☐					
Publications by experts (books, articles, internet, etc.)	☐					
External consultancy (private providers)	☐					
<i>Chile, the Netherlands & Norway:</i> Students' and/or parents' surveys	☐					
<i>Chile:</i> Feedback from the Supervisor of the Ministry of Education	☐					
<i>Chile:</i> Feedback from the Quality Agency	☐					
<i>Norway:</i> Medarbejderundersøkelse	☐					
<i>Chile:</i> Feedback and supervision from the Sostenedor	☐					
<i>Chile:</i> Results of SEPA test	☐					
<i>The Netherlands:</i> Feedback from the school board	☐					
Other, please specify:	☐					

---Page Break---

IN THIS SCHOOL, WHO EVALUATES YOUR WORK?

Please mark as many options as appropriate.

- *Catalonia & Madrid:* The school inspectorate
- *Chile:* The Quality agency and/or the Superintendence
- The principal and/or the management team
- *Norway:* The immediate leader
- Other teachers
- Yourself (self-evaluation)
- *Chile:* External consultant (private provider)
- Other, please specify:

---Page Break---

Display Question if Teachers' evaluation = The school inspectorate

WHICH TOOLS/SOURCES OF INFORMATION ARE USED BY THE INSPECTOR TO EVALUATE YOUR WORK?

Please mark as many choices as appropriate.

- Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...)
- Student results in the [national tests]
- Classroom observation
- Student and parent surveys
- Students' work and results in the classroom
- Other, please specify:

Display Question if Teachers' evaluation = The Quality agency and/or the Superintendence

WHICH TOOLS/SOURCES OF INFORMATION ARE USED BY THE AGENCY OF QUALITY AND/OR THE SUPERINTENDENCE TO EVALUATE YOUR WORK?

Please mark as many choices as appropriate.

- Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...)
- Student results in the [national tests]
- Classroom observation
- Results of the teachers' evaluation
- Student and parent surveys
- Students' work and results in the classroom
- Other, please specify:

Display Question if Teachers' evaluation = The immediate leader

WHICH TOOLS/SOURCES OF INFORMATION ARE USED BY THE IMMEDIATE LEADER TO EVALUATE YOUR WORK?

Please mark as many choices as appropriate.

- Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...)
- Student results in the [national tests]
- Classroom observation
- Student and parent surveys
- Students' work and results in the classroom
- Annual development meetings
- *Norway (secondary schools):* Analysis of your students' final exams' results
- Other, please specify: _____

---Page Break---

Display Question if Teachers' evaluation = Other teachers

WHICH TOOLS/SOURCES OF INFORMATION ARE USED BY OTHER TEACHERS TO EVALUATE YOUR WORK?

Please mark as many choices as appropriate.

- Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...)
- Classroom observation
- Other, please specify: _____

---Page Break---

Display Question if Teachers' evaluation = The principal and/or the management team

WHICH TOOLS/SOURCES OF INFORMATION ARE USED BY THE PRINCIPAL AND/OR MANAGEMENT TEAM TO EVALUATE YOUR WORK?

Please mark as many choices as appropriate.

- Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...)
- Student results in the [national tests]
- Classroom observation
- *Chile:* Results of the teachers' evaluation
- Student and parent surveys
- Students' work and results in the classroom
- *Norway:* Annual development meetings
- *Chile:* Results of other external tests (as for example SEPA)
- *Norway (secondary schools):* Analysis of your students' final exams' results
- Other, please specify: _____

---Page Break---

Display Question if Teachers' evaluation = Yourself (self-evaluation)

WHICH TOOLS/SOURCES OF INFORMATION DO YOU USE TO EVALUATE YOUR OWN WORK?

Please mark as many choices as appropriate.

- Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...)
- Student results in the [national tests]
- Student and parent surveys
- Students' work and results in the classroom
- Chile: Resultados de otras pruebas externas (por ejemplo, prueba SEPA)
- Norway (secondary schools): Analysis of your students' final exams' results
- Other, please specify: _____

---Page Break---

DISPLAY QUESTION IF TEACHERS' EVALUATION = EXTERNAL CONSULTANT (PRIVATE PROVIDER)

WHICH TOOLS/SOURCES OF INFORMATION ARE USED BY THE EXTERNAL CONSULTANT TO EVALUATE YOUR WORK?

Please mark as many choices as appropriate.

- Document analysis (portfolio, teaching plan...)
- Student results in the [national tests]
- Classroom observation
- Results of the teachers' evaluation
- Student and parent surveys
- Students' work and results in the classroom
- SEPA tests
- Other, please specify: _____

---Page Break---

IN COMPARISON TO OTHER SCHOOLS IN THE SCHOOL LOCAL COMMUNITY, HOW IS THE REPUTATION OF YOUR SCHOOL?

- Considerably above average
- Above average
- Average
- Below average
- Considerably below average

---Page Break---

WE WILL NOW DESCRIBE A HYPOTHETICAL SITUATION A TEACHER COULD FACE (IN YOUR COUNTRY OR ABROAD) FOLLOWED BY A FEW QUESTIONS.

[Female/male name] is a teacher working at a school in a [vulnerable/middle-class] neighbourhood of [capital city].

Next week a new national test, already implemented in other countries, will be conducted for the first time in the grade in which [name of the teacher] teaches.

For [name of the teacher] is very important that her students get good results in the test.

Baseline condition/control: [-]

[Treatment 1] In case of bad test results, the school owner will reduce the funding given to [female/male name]'s school.

[Treatment 2] In case of bad test results, [female/male name] will stop receiving her salary bonus.

[Treatment 3] In case of bad test results, [female/male name]'s school reputation will be damaged by the publication of the results in the media.

[Treatment 4] In case of bad test results, [female/male name]'s reputation as a teacher will be damaged by the publication of her class' results.

A colleague of [name of the teacher] advises her/him that to increase the probability of getting good results in the test, she/he should send her/him low-performing students to the school library to do an alternative activity during the hours of the test.

HOW LIKELY DO YOU THINK IT IS THAT THE TEACHER WILL FOLLOW THIS ADVICE?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not likely at all" and 7 indicates "Extremely likely".

- 7 Extremely likely
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 Not at all likely

---Page Break---

IF THE SAME SITUATION EXPERIENCED BY [FEMALE/MALE NAME] WERE TO HAPPEN TO YOU IN YOUR CURRENT SCHOOL, HOW LIKELY WOULD YOU BE TO FOLLOW THIS ADVICE?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all likely" and 7 indicates "Extremely likely".

- 7 Extremely likely
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 Not at all likely

---Page Break---

THE FOLLOWING QUESTIONS WILL FOCUS ON THE NATIONAL TEST AND ON THE DATA THAT THIS TEST GENERATES.

---Page Break---

Display Question if case is not The Netherlands

THIS SCHOOL YEAR, ARE YOU TEACHING A GRADE-LEVEL THAT WILL TAKE/HAS TAKEN PART IN TEST?]

- Yes
- No

IN THE PAST, HAVE YOU EVER TAUGHT A GRADE-LEVEL THAT TOOK PART IN THE [NATIONAL TEST]?

- Yes, within the last three years
- Yes, but more than three years ago
- No

---Page Break---

Display Question if Ever prepared students for the test is not No Or currently preparing for the test = Yes Or If case = The Netherlands And grade taught = Eighth

DO YOU HAVE ACCESS TO YOUR STUDENTS' INDIVIDUAL SCORES ON THE [NATIONAL TEST]?

- Yes
- No

---Page Break---

IN YOUR SCHOOL, WHAT ARE THE RESULTS OF [NATIONAL TEST] USED FOR?

(Multiple answers possible)

- To define and monitor our school improvement plan.
- To identify students with a need for more support and follow-up
- To assess teachers' work
- To take decisions about professional development activities for teachers
- To inform parents about the school achievement
- To group students (by achievement) for instructional purposes.
- To reward well-performing teachers
- To compare our performance with that of other schools
- To adjust the curriculum accordingly
- *Not Norway:* To report among the teaching staff
- *Catalonia & Madrid (secondary schools):* To help stream students into secondary education
- To build the school's reputation

IN THIS SCHOOL DO YOU CONSIDER IT DIFFICULT TO TRANSFORM NATIONAL TEST DATA TO CONCRETE MEASURES/ACTIONS TO IMPROVE YOUR TEACHING?

- Absolutely
- A lot
- To some extent
- A little
- Not at all

---Page Break---

Display Question if Capacity to use the data is not Not at all

WHAT FACTORS COULD EXPLAIN THESE DIFFICULTIES?

- The interpretation of the data requires statistical competences
- Data are not provided at the student level
- Data do not tell me anything I did not know before
- The report is not clear
- Lack of time to analyse/use the data
- Data/the report are not accessible
- Other, please specify: _____

---Page Break---

Display Question if Ever prepared students for the test is not No Or currently preparing for the test = Yes Or If grade taught = Eighth And case = The Netherlands

	No, never	Yes, it has been recommended	Yes, it has been instructed
HAVE THE PRINCIPAL AND THE MANAGEMENT TEAM RECOMMENDED AND/OR INSTRUCTED THAT TEACHING SHOULD BE MORE ADJUSTED TO THE ACHIEVEMENT OF THE EVALUABLE LEARNING STANDARDS?	☐	☐	☐
HAVE THE PRINCIPAL AND THE MANAGEMENT TEAM RECOMMENDED AND/OR INSTRUCTED THAT STUDENTS SHOULD PRACTICE FOR [NATIONAL TEST]?	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

	Not at all/None at all	A little	Some	A lot	Completely
All cases, except Norway: IN YOUR SCHOOL HAS [NATIONAL TEST] LED TO A REDISTRIBUTION OF RESOURCES (TIME, PERSONNEL, AND BUDGET) IN FAVOR OF THE SUBJECT AREAS AND COMPETENCES THAT ARE TESTED?	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
TO WHAT EXTENT HAS THE EXISTENCE OF LEARNING STANDARDS INFLUENCED THE PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH OF THIS SCHOOL?	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
IN YOUR SCHOOL, TO WHAT EXTENT IS [NATIONAL TEST] TAKEN INTO ACCOUNT WHEN TAKING DECISIONS ABOUT CURRICULAR CONTENT?	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Norway: IN YOUR SCHOOL HAS [NATIONAL TEST] LED TO A REDISTRIBUTION OF RESOURCES (TIME, PERSONNEL, AND BUDGET) IN FAVOR OF THE COMPETENCES THAT ARE TESTED?	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

Display Question if Ever prepared students for the test is not No Or If currently preparing for the test = Yes Or If case = The Netherlands And grade taught = Eighth

DO YOU CONDUCT ACTIVITIES WITH YOUR STUDENTS THAT FOCUS ON PREPARING THEM FOR [NATIONAL TEST]? (SUCH AS PRACTICING ON PREVIOUS TESTS/EXAMPLE QUESTIONS, ETC.)

- Yes, during the whole year
- Yes, but only during the month before the test
- No, never

---Page Break---

Display Question if Teaching to the test = Yes, during the whole year

HOW OFTEN DO YOU CONDUCT ACTIVITIES WITH YOUR STUDENTS THAT FOCUS ON PREPARING THEM FOR [NATIONAL TEST]? (SUCH AS PRACTICING ON PREVIOUS TESTS/EXAMPLE QUESTIONS, ETC.)

	Seldom (once a month)	Occasionally (several times a month)	Frequently (several times a week)	In every class
During the whole year	☐	☐	☐	☐

Display Question if Teaching to the test = Yes, during the whole year

AND DURING THE MONTH BEFORE THE TEST?

- Once or twice
- Once a week
- Several times a week
- In every class

Display Question if Teaching to the test = Yes, but only during the month before the test

HOW OFTEN DO YOU CONDUCT ACTIVITIES WITH YOUR STUDENTS THAT FOCUS ON PREPARING THEM FOR [NATIONAL TEST]? (SUCH AS PRACTICING ON PREVIOUS TESTS/EXAMPLE QUESTIONS, ETC.)

	Once or twice	Once a week	Several times a week	In every class
During the month before the test	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

IN YOUR OPINION, HOW MUCH IMPORTANCE IS GIVEN TO THE [NATIONAL TEST] IN THE CURRENT PUBLIC EDUCATIONAL DEBATE?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all important" and 7 indicates "Extremely important".

- Not at all important 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- Extremely important 7

---Page Break---

TO YOUR KNOWLEDGE, DO THE RESULTS OF [NATIONAL TEST] HAVE ANY KIND OF CONSEQUENCES (ECONOMIC, WORK-RELATED, REPUTATIONAL, ETC.) FOR ANY OF THE FOLLOWING ACTORS?

(Multiple answers possible)

- For the principal
- For teachers
- All cases, except The Netherlands: For students
- Norway: For the school owner
- For the school
- The Netherlands: For the school board
- Norway (not public schools): For the school board
- No consequences
- I do not know

---Page Break---

Display Question if Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom is not No consequences

And Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom is not I do not know

WHAT ARE THE CONSEQUENCES OF THE [NATIONAL TEST]?

(Multiple choice possible)

Display Question if Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom = For the principal

FOR THE PRINCIPAL:

- Salary bonus
- Increases or decreases of the principal's salary
- The principal can be withdrawn from his/her position
- Impact on professional reputation
- Other, please specify: _____
- I do not know the exact consequences

Display Question if Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom = For teachers

FOR TEACHERS

- Salary bonus
- Teachers' tenure/promotion decisions
- Salary increases or decreases
- Provision of professional development (training and attendance to conferences, mentoring, individual/collaborative research)
- Impact on professional reputation
- Other, please specify: _____
- I do not know the exact consequences

Display Question if Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom = For students

FOR STUDENTS

- Student grade promotion or graduation
- Rewards for students
- Other, please specify: _____
- I do not know the exact consequences

Display Question if Knowledge of the consequences attached to the test – for whom = For the school

FOR THE SCHOOL:

- *Chile & The Netherlands:* The school is more closely monitored by the ministry
- School closure
- *All cases, except Norway:* Award of a collective salary bonus
- Impact on the school reputation
- The educational authority provides extra support/resources to the school
- *Catalonia & Madrid:* The school is more closely monitored by the inspectorate
- *Chile:* The school is more closely monitored by the agency of quality
- *Norway (not public schools):* The school is more closely monitored by the school board
- *Norway (public schools):* The school is more closely monitored by the school owner
- *The Netherlands:* The school is more closely monitored by the school board
- Other, please specify: _____
- I do not know the exact consequences

---Page Break---

Display Question if currently preparing for the test = No And Ever prepared students for the test = No Or If case = The Netherlands And grade taught is not Eighth

IN YOUR OPINION, HOW MUCH PRESSURE DO TEACHERS IN THIS SCHOOL FEEL TO GET GOOD RESULTS IN [NATIONAL TEST]?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates “None at all” and 7 indicates “An extreme amount”.

- None at all 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- An extreme amount 7

Display Question if currently preparing for the test = Yes And Ever prepared students for the test = Yes Or If case = The Netherlands And grade taught is Eighth

HOW MUCH PRESSURE DO YOU FEEL TO GET GOOD RESULTS IN [NATIONAL TEST]?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates “None at all” and 7 indicates “An extreme amount”.

- None at all 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- An extreme amount 7

---Page Break---

Display Question if Perception of own pressures is not None at all Or perceptions of other pressures is not None at all

TO WHAT EXTENT DOES THIS PRESSURE COME FROM THE FOLLOWING ACTORS?

Please indicate your answer on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 indicates "Not at all" and 7 indicates "Extremely".

	Not at all 1	2	3	4	5	6	Extremely 7
Ministry of Education - Federal/Central authority	☐						
Chile: Quality Agency	☐						
Chile: Superintendence	☐						
Norway: Regional authority	☐						
Catalonia & Madrid: Autonomic/regional authority	☐						
Chile (public schools), The Netherlands & Norway: Municipality authority	☐						
The Netherlands: Supervisor/School board	☐						
Catalonia, Madrid & The Netherlands: Inspector	☐						
All cases, except The Netherlands (not public schools): School board/Private school owner	☐						
Principal and/or the management team	☐						
All cases, except Norway: School Council	☐						
Other teachers	☐						
Parents	☐						
Self-imposed pressure	☐						
The media	☐						
Other, please specify	☐						

---Page Break---

WE WOULD LIKE TO KNOW YOUR OPINIONS ON [NATIONAL TEST] AND OTHER IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF THE SCHOOL ORGANISATION.

DO YOU THINK THAT A SCHOOL'S [NATIONAL TEST] RESULTS INFLUENCE ITS REPUTATION?

- Not at all
- A little
- To some extent
- A lot
- Absolutely

DO YOU THINK IT IS IMPORTANT FOR TEACHERS IN THIS SCHOOL THAT THEIR STUDENTS OUTPERFORM THOSE OF OTHER CLASSES IN THE [NATIONAL TEST]?

Please consider both other classes of the same grades and of different grades.

- Not at all
- A little
- To some extent
- A lot
- Absolutely

---Page Break---

TO WHAT EXTENT DO YOU THINK THAT IT IS FAIR...

	Very unfair	Unfair	Fair	Very fair
... to measure the quality of a school based on [national test] results?	○	○	○	○
... to publicly disseminate [national test] results in the media and/or internet?	○	○	○	○
... that schools with different characteristics are compared on the basis of their [national test] results?	○	○	○	○

---Page Break---

IN YOUR OPINION, TO WHAT EXTENT DOES A SCHOOL'S SCORE IN [NATIONAL TEST] REFLECT THE EFFORTS AND ABILITY OF THE INDIVIDUAL TEACHERS?

- Completely
- A lot
- To some extent
- A little
- Not at all

○ ---Page Break---

TO WHAT EXTENT DO YOU AGREE OR DISAGREE WITH THE FOLLOWING STATEMENTS?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Preparation for [national test] takes too much time away from more important activities in the school	○	○	○	○	○
The content of [national test] tells us what the school's priorities are	○	○	○	○	○
The results of [national test] do not provide useful information on student learning	○	○	○	○	○
A good teacher can be recognized by his/her students' results in [national test]	○	○	○	○	○
The results of [national test] do not adequately represent what students have learned and can do	○	○	○	○	○

○ ---Page Break---

IN YOUR OPINION, FOR A SCHOOL TO WORK WELL, WHO SHOULD BE RESPONSIBLE OF THE FOLLOWING DOMAINS?

(Multiple answers possible)

- | | |
|---|--|
| Budget allocation | |
| Selection of school principals | |
| Selection of new teachers | |
| <i>All cases, except Norway:</i> Teachers' salary increases/Teachers' promotion | ▪ Educational authorities/administration |
| <i>All cases, except Norway:</i> Students' admission into the school | ▪ Principal and/or leadership team |
| <i>All cases, except the NL:</i> Curriculum adjustment (curricular objectives and/or content) | ▪ <i>All cases, except Norway and the NL:</i> School council |
| <i>For the NL:</i> Curriculum development | ▪ <i>For the NL:</i> Medezeggenschapsraad |
| Choice of textbooks and teaching materials | ▪ Teachers |
| Content of in-service training | |
| Assessment of teaching quality | |
| Teaching methods | |
| Students' assessment criteria and procedures | |
| <i>For the NL:</i> Choice of eindtoets | |
| <i>For the NL:</i> Choice of LVS | |
| The raising and use of private funds | |

---Page Break---

NOW, WE WOULD LIKE TO ASK YOU SOME QUESTIONS ON HOW YOU FEEL IN RELATION TO YOUR WORK.

TO WHAT EXTENT DO YOU AGREE OR DISAGREE WITH THE FOLLOWING STATEMENTS?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
I would like to move to another school if it were possible	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I enjoy working at this school	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I would recommend my school as a good place to work	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I regret that I decided to become a teacher	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I wonder whether it would have been better to choose another profession	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
If I could decide again, I would still choose to work as a teacher	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
All in all, I am satisfied with my job	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

TO WHAT EXTENT DO YOU AGREE OR DISAGREE WITH THE FOLLOWING STATEMENTS?

	Strongly disagree	Moderately disagree	Disagree slightly more than agree	Agree slightly more than disagree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree
If a student did not remember information I gave in a previous lesson, I would know how to increase his/her retention in the next lesson	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
If a student in my class becomes disruptive and noisy, I feel assured that I know some techniques to redirect him/her quickly	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
If students aren't disciplined at home, they aren't likely to accept any discipline at school	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
A teacher is very limited in what he/she can achieve because a student's home environment has a large influence on his/her achievement	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
When it comes right down to it, a teacher really can't do much because most of a student's motivation and performance depends on his or her home environment	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
If I really try hard, I can get through to even the most difficult or unmotivated students	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

IS YOUR CURRENT CONTRACT IN THIS SCHOOL A...

- Permanent contract
- For the NL and Norway: Fixed term contract, more than 3 years
- Fixed term contract, 1-3 years
- Fixed term contract, less than 1 year
- For Chile: "Contracto a honorarios"

Display This Question if case = Catalonia Or Madrid And Leadership function in the school is not principal Or If case is the Netherlands

IS YOUR EMPLOYMENT IN THIS SCHOOL:

- Full time
- Part time

---Page Break---

Display Question if Type of contract = Part time

ARE YOU CURRENTLY WORKING IN ANY OTHER SCHOOL?

- No
- Yes, in a public school
- Yes, in a private school
- Yes, in an independent publicly funded school

---Page Break---

Display Question if case is not Norway

ARE YOU A MEMBER OF A PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATION (COLLEGIAL OR PEDAGOGICAL) OR DO YOU TAKE PART IN A CAMPAIGN OR PLATFORM IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION?

- Yes
- No

ARE YOU A MEMBER OF A TEACHER UNION?

- Yes
- No
- Norway: I prefer not to answer

---Page Break---

Display Question if Professional association membership = Yes

PLEASE INDICATE THE NAME OF THE ASSOCIATION/S OR PLATFORMS/CAMPAIGNS YOU ARE A MEMBER OF:
[Context-sensitive list of associations/platforms/campaigns]

Display Question if Union membership = Yes

WHICH UNION ARE YOU A MEMBER OF?

(Context-sensitive list of teachers' unions)

WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING DEGREES/CERTIFICATES DO YOU HOLD?

(Multiple answers possible)

[Context-sensitive list of degrees/certificates]

---Page Break---

Display Question if more than 1 degree/certificate were selected

WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING DEGREE/S HAS/HAVE GIVEN YOU THE RIGHT TO TEACH?

[List of previously selected degrees/certificate]

---Page Break---

Display Question if degrees/certificates is Equal to 1

IN WHAT YEAR/S DID YOU COMPLETE THIS DEGREE?

[Dropdown menu with years]

---Page Break---

BEFORE ENDING THIS SURVEY, WE WOULD LIKE TO KNOW YOUR OPINION ON A FEW NON-EDUCATIONAL MATTERS.

TO WHAT EXTENT DO YOU AGREE OR DISAGREE WITH THE FOLLOWING STATEMENTS?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
The government should take measures to reduce differences in income levels	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Workers need strong trade unions to protect their working conditions and wages	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The less the government intervenes in the economy, the better it is for the country	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

---Page Break---

THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR PARTICIPATING IN OUR SURVEY!

WOULD YOU BE INTERESTED IN THE RESULTS OF THIS STUDY?

- Yes, I would like to receive a report with the main findings of this study
- Yes, I would like to receive an invitation to the devolution seminar, organized in [city] on [date]
- No

WOULD YOU LIKE TO PARTICIPATE IN THE PRIZE DRAW OF [SPECIFY PRIZE]?

- Yes
- No

--Page Break--

Display Question if one of the previous questions is = Yes

PLEASE PROVIDE AN E-MAIL ADDRESS THAT WE CAN USE TO INFORM YOU IN THE FUTURE ABOUT THE RESULTS OF THIS STUDY AND/OR ABOUT THE RESULTS OF THE PRIZE DRAW:

o ---Page Break---

IS THERE ANYTHING ELSE YOU WOULD LIKE TO COMMENT ON WITH REGARD TO QUESTIONS OR THEMES THAT YOU THINK SHOULD BE EXPLORED FURTHER?
